

Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions, and Limerence
among Young Adults

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Abstract

Adverse childhood experiences can cause fear of abandonment and thinking errors related to one's relationships in later life. As the individuals cross the maze of human connection, they may also encounter the intense experience of limerence which is an overwhelming state marked by deep infatuation and romantic obsession. Several research have explored how adverse childhood experiences can cause significant issues in adulthood, but this research aimed to investigate how interpersonal cognitive distortions mediate the relationship between fear of abandonment, and limerence among Pakistani youth. This research also aimed to explore the effect of gender and relationship status on the relationship between variables. It was a correlational study and based on purposive sampling strategy a sample of N=332 was taken from different universities of Lahore. The data was collected through a series of questionnaires including demographic questionnaire, Abandonment Core Belief Self-Assessment (Skeen, 2014), Wolf & Lemay Limerence Measure (Wolf & Lemay, 2015), and Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions Scale (Hamamci, 2004). The data collected was analyzed through SPSS v26. The findings indicated that fear of abandonment is significantly positively correlated with interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence. Complementary mediation was indicated for interpersonal cognitive distortions and partial mediation for unrealistic relationship expectations in the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence. Moreover, it was found that women scored significantly higher on fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence as compared to men. People who were in a complicated or uncertain relationship scored highest on study variables. The findings of the study can be utilized in making individualized intervention plans to address these issues in youth.

Keywords: Fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, limerence, young adults, gender differences

Introduction

Overtime and across cultures young adulthood has been described as the delicate stage of human growth, emerges as a period of particularly exciting, confusing, and trans-formative phase, at both intrapersonal and interpersonal levels (Bogaerts et al., 2021; Branje et al., 2012). As Erikson proposed in his famous psycho-social theory, young adulthood is the time when an individual's major life concern is to make intimate, committed, and close relationships (Erikson, 1993). They must balance the imperative need to engage in meaningful connections while also confronting the intimidating spectre of isolation (Montgomery, 2005). According to a lot of social psychologists and sociologists humans are considered to be as social beings, and other times also referred as social animals (Sakman, 2019) which very well resonates with Maslow's hierarchy of needs, especially where he emphasizes on one of the most fundamental need to be loved, belong to or feel connected to others (Maslow, 1943). In simple words, humans are dependent on others to survive.

Some young adults are unable to make stable interpersonal connections due to their adverse childhood experiences (Estric et al., 2022; Poole et al., 2018; Stevens et al., 2013). Much research has supported that an individual's attachment styles are shaped by early childhood experiences (Özcan et al., 2016). Adverse childhood experiences including physical, emotional, sexual abuse, and neglect develop maladaptive attachment patterns including anxious, avoidant, or disorganized (Özcan et al., 2016; Thomson & Jaque, 2017; Toof et al., 2020). Attachment patterns are significant predictor of adult relationships (Widom et al., 2018). Individuals may not knowingly copy the patterns formed in their childhood, in their relationships they form in adulthood (Lassri et al., 2016). And if their experiences were negative, they may not be able to form adaptive and secure relationships in their adulthood. The blueprint for adult relationships is

unconsciously based on the dynamics of their childhood maladaptive experiences, maintaining a cycle of discomfort and pathology (Shahab et al., 2021).

As an individual gets older, the emphasis of the interpersonal relationships shifts from family, friends, and classmates to romantic partners (Bogaerts et al., 2021). Because attachment is a basic human need, it's understandable that one of the greatest fears is the possibility of being rejected or abandoned (Keller, 2016; Palihawadana et al., 2018). But when this fear becomes intrusive and starts sabotaging the relationships, it could be indicative of a firm core belief or schema of abandonment (Palihawadana et al., 2018). The individual's childhood and adolescent experiences create their core beliefs or in other words schema. Schema is basically a mental structure, a framework that helps an individual to organize and make sense of new information and model their cognitions and behaviors (Bartlett, 2017). These mental structures, or rules are formed in a way that all the new information is processed, and the brain tries to fit it into these frameworks (Arntz & Genderen, 2020). Every individual has schemata or core beliefs, carried on in the adulthood and their work is to guide the individual's beliefs about themselves, others, and the world (Bartlett, 2017). Young explained an early maladaptive schema in his schema theory as a comprehensive, deep and permanent pattern including memories, feelings, thoughts, and physical sensations about an individual's self and their interpersonal relationships (Young et al., 2006). According to him, these schemata develop over time, persist throughout individual's life, and significantly impair their daily functioning.

Among all those 18 types of schemata that Young proposed, schema or the core belief of abandonment arises from childhood or adolescent experiences such as physical or emotional loss, a dearth of emotional support or connection, or exposure to an unstable and unreliable environment (Young et al., 2006). The core belief of abandonment is the fear that the people an

individual can rely on for support and connection are not stable or dependable. It's basically the belief that they might be emotionally unstable, unpredictable, or might leave for someone else, leaving the individual without emotional support or protection (Palihawadana et al., 2018). There will be situations or interactions that remind an individual of a painful experience from their childhood, related to getting abandoned and the schema will be triggered. In response to the triggered schema of abandonment or any other maladaptive schema, the individual will have physical, behavioral, cognitive, and emotional symptoms or signs (Skeen, 2014). One of the behavioral responses some people with fear of abandonment show is getting obsessed with the people, because deep down there is the fear of getting left alone, so the individual clings and gets obsessed with people around.

As Tennov (1979) explained limerence is basically an intense state of romantic obsession marked by intrusive thoughts about a desired romantic partner. Individuals in this state desire reciprocation from the limerent object (LO) and most often experience extreme emotional fluctuations based on the perceived reciprocation. The individuals may struggle with insecurities, idealize the LO, and seek exclusivity in the relationship. They often use their fantasies about mutual affection as their coping and to get relief. As discussed earlier, there is a strong relationship between attachment styles and core belief of abandonment and when this core belief gets triggered, in some individuals it manifests itself in the behavioral response of limerence. There is also strong evidence that limerence is linked with anxious attachment style because adult romantic attraction is also an attachment process (Feeney & Noller, 1990; Hazan & Shaver, 1987). Among three attachment styles, anxious attachment is somehow similar to the state of limerence, as both involve a desire for closeness and a fear of rejection or abandonment. However, while they share some similarities, they are not entirely synonymous concepts (Wolf,

2017). The shared experience of interpersonal rejection indicates a relationship between anxious attachment and limerence (Hazan & Shaver, 1987). It can be concluded that individuals with an anxious attachment style might be more susceptible to experiencing limerence compared to those with avoidant or secure attachment styles (Wolf, 2017).

Cognitive distortions or cognitive errors are systematic errors or biases in thinking, in information processing that alter incoming information to align with existing schemas and can lead to inaccurate perceptions of reality and negative interpretations of events. Cognitive distortions are one of the three mechanisms through which schemas are perpetuated, the other two are self-defeating life patterns and maladaptive schema coping strategies the individuals use. Cognitive distortions lead individuals to perceive situations in a way that either strengthens existing schemas, intensifying the information that aligns with the schema while minimizing or dismissing the information which contradicts the schema “confirmatory bias”. When the maladaptive schemas are triggered, its cognitive consequences in the form of cognitive distortions, lead the individuals' minds to follow familiar patterns, prioritizing negative memories and disregarding positive information that contradicts their schemas. The cognitive distortions which maintain the schema of abandonment are most commonly catastrophizing, all or none thinking, personalization, jumping to conclusion, self-fulfilling prophecy, and mind reading. In interpersonal relationships, whenever the schema of abandonment is triggered, the relationships are mostly affected by the cognitive distortions an individual holds about the relationships, and this roots deep down in their early experiences and attachment styles.

Interpersonal cognitive distortions are entrenched, irrational thought patterns that significantly exaggerate the nature of relationships and lead to misinterpretations of life events. As described by DiGiuseppe and Zee (1986), these rigid relationship patterns result in a limited

repertoire of social roles. According to Hamamcı (2004), these rigid patterns within relationships can be categorized into three types: interpersonal rejection (avoidance of intimacy), unrealistic relationship expectations, and interpersonal misperception (mind-reading). Interpersonal rejection reflects individuals' beliefs that forming close relationships will lead to negative consequences. Unrealistic relationship expectations involve expecting high levels of performance from both oneself and others in relationships. Finally, interpersonal misperception entails trying to understand the thoughts and feelings of others through unrealistic methods. These cognitive distortions have a significant impact on how individuals communicate with others, often creating barriers to effective communication. People develop these interpersonal cognitive distortions based on their schemas or core belief systems and family scripts.

When the schemas are triggered, the individual perceives it as a threat and responds to it using the maladaptive coping styles which can be either schema surrender, schema avoidance or schema overcompensation. In case of schema of abandonment, if the individual is using the coping style of overcompensation, they may excessively cling to and overwhelm their partner. Limerence somehow can be said as a response to schema of abandonment as both have roots in early experiences and maladaptive attachment styles. Limerence can be seen as a schema overcompensation of abandonment that due to the fear of being left alone, an individual fight the schema by thinking, feeling, behaving, and relating completely as opposite of the schema.

Rationale of the Study

This study aims to explore the relationship between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence among young adults in Pakistan. This research would provide invaluable insights for the clinical psychologists, psychotherapists, and other mental health professionals to understand the complex interaction of engraved abandonment schema, the

cognitive errors arise from it, affecting interpersonal relationships and the manifestation of limerence among young adults as a behavioral consequence of the underlying schema of abandonment. Understanding this interaction is important for professionals and can be helpful in devising effective therapeutic interventions to help youth struggling with these distressing cognitive and emotional states. Furthermore, this research aimed to shed light on the highly overlooked emotional phenomenon of limerence, offering mental health professionals an in-depth understanding of underlying processes, to develop individualized therapeutic approaches for youth experiencing it.

Chapter II

Literature Review

Review of the literature incorporates the historical background, symptoms, development, and therapeutic treatment options for schema of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence. Different theories and models that have been used to explain fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence are incorporated along with the theories and models that may provide some possible in-depth understanding. The limited previous research on these variables is also discussed. Moreover, the link of fear of abandonment and limerence with borderline personality disorder is also highlighted. Furthermore, the connection of variables with each other is also discussed using previous research. Special attention is paid to the rising prevalence of these cognitive, and emotive states in Pakistani culture.

Fear of Abandonment

Fear is defined as a deeply distressing emotional response when a danger or threat is perceived or acknowledged, it is somehow like anxiety as it reflects an apprehension of potential future threats that are perceived to be beyond of control (Öhman, 1993). Abandonment is characterized by the act of being left behind by an individual or entity, or the cessation of something, typically for forever. It includes significant withdrawal of care and responsibility by someone towards a dependent. Masterson (1972) delineated the concept of fear of abandonment for the first time within the framework of borderline personality construct. It was also said that it resonates deeply with the fear of aloneness (Gunderson & Singer, 1975). This section of literature review includes an in-depth understanding of fear of abandonment.

Symptoms of Fear of Abandonment

Fear of abandonment manifests itself as a persistent anxiety that generates maladaptive emotional responses and behavioral patterns, exacerbating the cycle of distress within interpersonal relationships. Individuals afraid of abandonment suffer from a variety of symptoms. These symptoms can vary from individual to individual. It includes profound distress, panic attacks or panic symptoms when the realistic or unrealistic fear of abandonment is triggered, pervasive difficulty in placing trust in others. Hypersensitivity to criticism and a perpetual fear of intimacy is also very common which significantly affects interpersonal relationships. Individuals with this anxiety find themselves trapped in unhealthy relationships, driven by an overpowering fear of isolation, and may display signs of codependency. There is a tendency towards engaging in impulsive behaviors, for instance, unwanted sexual encounters whenever the fear is triggered. Paradoxically, they may also engage in behaviors that sabotage relationships, pushing others away defensively to avoid the pain of perceived abandonment (Palihawadana et al., 2018).

Theories Explaining Fear of Abandonment

Fear of abandonment could be explained by many theories and models. A brief description of the theories is considered.

Bolby's Attachment Theory. In his pioneering work, Bowlby postulated that all infants have an innate tendency to develop an attachment to their caregivers, and that the infant's beliefs of security and lovability are shaped by the caregiver's responsiveness and closeness (Bowlby, 1989). Inadequate caring, resulting from mentally ill parent(s) or misinterpreting their child's needs, hinders the formation of a solid and realistic self-concept (LaRossa & Rutter, 1982). Children who experience a lack of stable connection at an early age are more vulnerable to

experiencing fear of abandonment and other negative emotions, which might overwhelm their ability to control their impulses and desires (Hazan et al., 2004). When newborns are abandoned, their existence depends on someone else, which exacerbates fear and uncertainty in close connections. Every part of life is impacted by this fear of abandonment, which affects attention and prevents efficient stress management (Van IJzendoorn & Sagi, 1999).

Moreover, core beliefs about oneself and others are profoundly influenced by the traits of caregivers that correspond to distinct attachment types, such as rejection and harshness in avoidantly attached children or inconsistency and chaos in ambivalently attached children (Fonagy & Bateman, 2008). Later research by Ainsworth refined insecure attachment styles, emphasizing how often anxious/ambivalent and disorganized/disoriented styles are prevalent in people with Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD), in their clinical presentation (Ainsworth et al., 1978). Research has supported that fear of abandonment is very closely associated with insecure attachment style (Bowlby, 1989; Palihawadana et al., 2018; Skeen, 2014; Temple, 2003; Young et al., 2003).

Young's Schema Theory. According to Young's Schema Theory (Young et al., 2003), early maladaptive schemas develop mainly because of adverse childhood experiences. These events interfere with the fulfilment of basic emotional needs, which causes early maladaptive schemas to form and alter how a person views the world and themselves. Young et al., (2003) distinguished four main categories of early adverse childhood experiences that were favorable to the formation of schemas. Among them, the schema of abandonment or emotional deprivation is a result when the child suffers toxic frustration of needs due to inadequate affection, stability, or nurturing. A schema of abandonment, which is a sense of perceived instability in relationships with significant others, resulting from emotional volatility, unpredictable presence, and fears of

death, abandonment, or being replaced by someone better (Palihawadana et al., 2018; Young et al., 2003).

Negative childhood experiences, according to Young et al. (2003), interact with a child's innate disposition rather than acting alone. Children's perceptions and responses to negative stimuli are influenced by their temperament (Pérez-Edgar & Fox, 2007). Reactive temperaments might further contribute to the construction of early maladaptive schemas by impeding the fulfilment of important demands during development when combined with unfavorable experiences (Sójta & Strzelecki, 2023).

Neurobiological Theory. According to neurobiological perspective, traumatic experiences lead to the establishment of memories through two distinct systems in the brain. On conscious level, traumatic memories are encoded and stored by the hippocampus and related cortical areas, while on the unconscious level, traumatic memories are established by fear conditioning mechanisms facilitated by the amygdala (LeDoux, 1996). These parallel systems store different memories and aspects of the experience, with the amygdala focusing on emotional memory, while the hippocampus and neocortex store cognitive memory (Yang & Wang, 2017). The retrieval of these memories differs in nature when the individual encounters a stimulus which was present at the time of experience. The amygdala system triggers the automatic bodily responses preparing for danger, and the hippocampal system facilitates conscious recollection of memories (Weymar & Schwabe, 2016; Yang & Wang, 2017).

LeDoux proposed that the brain mechanisms responsible for registering, storing, and retrieving memories of traumatic events operate independently from those processing conscious memories and cognitions related to the same event (LeDoux, 1996). Emotional responses and bodily sensations related to childhood experiences are primarily stored in the amygdala, and they

can be activated automatically when the individual encounters stimuli reminiscent of past traumatic events (Cancel et al., 2017; Zhang, 2022). These are the traumatic experiences due to which an individual's schema of abandonment is developed. This activation occurs immediately and often on an unconscious level, and if it is on conscious level, it happens prior to cognitive recognition. These emotional and bodily sensations tend to persist over time once stored in the amygdala and shapes an individual's emotions and subsequent behaviors (Zhang, 2022). Conversely, cognitions associated with trauma and conscious memories are stored in the hippocampus and higher cortical regions (LeDoux, 1996; Teyler & DiScenna, 1985).

Dysfunctional Coping Modes of Schema of Abandonment

Schema modes are basically the emotional states and coping responses triggered by life situations or 'emotional buttons'. One of the schema modes given by Young et al., (2003) was dysfunctional coping modes. When the schemas are triggered, they are perceived as a threat, and it leads to the frustration of a core emotional need and subsequent emotions. Individuals respond to this with coping styles which are initially adaptive in childhood but become maladaptive as they get older because they maintain the maladaptive schemas. Following is the brief explanation of dysfunctional coping modes of schema of abandonment when triggered.

The Compliant Surrenderer (Schema Surrender). The compliant surrenderer of schema of abandonment becomes the helpless, docile child who must give in to others as they submit themselves to the schema. The individual with this coping doesn't try to resist or avoid the schema of abandonment. When the schema of abandonment is triggered the individual in a compliant surrenderer coping style will react emotionally disproportionately and they will fully experience the emotional distress. They behave in a way to confirm the schema, for instance, they will get involved with the partners who are emotionally unavailable, and who cannot

commit. Examples are getting attracted to someone who is already in a relationship, or someone with significant differences. They choose to remain in toxic relationships with the partners who treat them as offending parents.

The Detached Protector (Schema Avoidance). Individuals who use avoidance as a coping mechanism make arrangements in their lives to ensure that the schema of abandonment is never triggered. They try not to experience the schema. Whenever emotions arise, they instinctively suppress them. Individuals with detached protector coping psychologically retreats from the agony of schema of abandonment by emotional detachment, misusing drugs, self-overstimulating, avoiding social situations, or adopting other escape mechanisms including promiscuous sexual behavior, compulsive cleaning, overreacting or they may become workaholics.

The Over-compensator (Schema Overcompensation). Overcompensation occurs because it provides an escape from the suffering caused by the schema of abandonment. It is a way for the individuals to get away from the helplessness and vulnerability they experienced as children. Individuals who use overcompensation as a coping to disprove the schema of abandonment will mistreat others or exhibit harsh outbursts. Individuals who overcompensate resist the schema by acting, feeling, thinking, and interacting in ways that are consistent with the schema's antithesis. They viciously fight with the partner for even the smallest of separations, or cling to and "smothers" the partner to the point of pushing them away.

Schema of Abandonment and Cognitive Distortions

Cognitive distortions are one of the three mechanisms through which schemas are perpetuated (Young et al., 2003). Cognitive distortions lead individuals to perceive situations in a way that either strengthens existing schemas, intensifying the information that aligns with the

schema while minimizing or dismissing the information which contradicts the schema “confirmatory bias” (Young et al., 2003). All of the individual's self-fulfilling prophecies, all of the beliefs, feelings, and behaviors that ultimately serve to reinforce rather than to cure the schema of abandonment are considered forms of perpetuation. The individual perceives situations incorrectly through cognitive distortions, emphasizing information that supports the schema and downplaying or ignoring information that contradicts it (Puri et al., 2021). This leads to the reinforcement of the schema.

Research on cognitive distortions arising from schema of abandonment is limited however as fear of abandonment is a core feature of Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) and the research related to cognitive distortions in BPD suggests that some cognitive errors including dichotomous thinking, belief inflexibility bias, thought abandonment fusion, labeling, jumping to conclusions, attribution bias, should statements, personalization, and catastrophizing are very common in individuals having BPD or BP traits (Arntz & Haaf, 2012; Moritz et al., 2011; Napolitano & McKay, 2007; Puri et al., 2018, 2021). Many of these distortions coincide with a schema mode, contributing to the maintenance and reinforcement of negative cognitions within that schema mode (Puri et al., 2021).

Fear of Abandonment and Limerence

There is a dearth of research relating fear or schema of abandonment with limerence, obsessive, or pathological love. However, both limerence and schema of abandonment have their roots in adverse childhood experiences and attachment styles. An individual having schema of abandonment, in their schema overcompensation mode, they may become clingy to their romantic partner. Limerence on the hand is the pathological picture of romantic obsession that is on each level including biological, cognitive, emotional, and behavioral.

Schema Therapy for Fear of Abandonment

Schema therapy is a therapeutic intervention developed by Young (1990, 1999) which goes beyond conventional cognitive-behavioral models by incorporating principles from attachment theory, cognitive-behavioral, Gestalt therapy, constructivist, object relation and psychoanalysis. It presents a comprehensive model for interpreting and addressing core beliefs or schemas embedded in early experiences, which often underlie chronic psychological disorders for instance, personality disorders. Schema therapy is the best therapeutic approach available for fear of abandonment because it employs techniques such as cognitive restructuring and experiential interventions, along with the goal of targeting early maladaptive schemas (Young et al., 2003).

Previous Research Related to Fear of Abandonment

There is a dearth of research on fear of abandonment, however the limited research focused on attachment styles, early experiences, and borderline personality disorder. Research by D’Rozario and Pilkington (2021) suggested that parental separation or divorce can significantly influence attachment styles and their impact in adulthood. Individuals with a history of parental divorce or separation tend to have anxious or avoidant attachment styles, and they develop the underlying abandonment schema. Moreover, according to Palihawadana et al. (2018) research finding, fear of abandonment emerges prominently in borderline personality disorder (BPD), and it's considered a core symptom. They found that this fear not only affects compliance with the treatment but also correlates with suicidal behavior and non-suicidal self-injury, thus affecting prognosis. Regardless of clinical significance of fear of abandonment, there's a noted lack of targeted treatment interventions.

Additionally, fear of abandonment manifests in various behaviors and psychological conditions. For instance, research conducted by Patton (1992) suggests that binge eating can

serve as a defense mechanism against unconscious fear of abandonment, aligning with psychoanalytic hypotheses. Similarly, in the context of sexual behavior as suggested by Willis and Nelson-Gray (2017), fear of abandonment moderates the association between BPD traits and sexual compliance, particularly evident in scenarios where participants anticipate poorly matched relationships. Moreover, another research by Wolchik et al. (2002) supports that fear of abandonment mediates the relationship between divorce stressors, mother-child relationship quality, and children's adjustment problems, emphasizing its role in familial dynamics and child development. Lastly, Zerubavel et al. (2017) concluded that in cases of intimate partner violence, the severity of dissociation is moderated by childhood sexual abuse severity and fear of abandonment, indicating complex interactions between trauma, fear of abandonment, and psychological outcomes. However, the association of fear of abandonment with interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence was never explored.

Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions

Cognitive distortions were originally defined by Beck (1967) as the result of processing information in ways that predictably resulted in identifiable errors in thinking. In his work with depressed patients, Beck defined six systematic errors in thinking: arbitrary inference; selective abstraction; overgeneralization; magnification and minimization; personalization; and absolutistic, dichotomous thinking. They give rise to dysfunctional behaviors and emotions while developing negative self-perceptions, negative views of others, and a pessimistic view of the world. These automatic thoughts are often far from reality and result from systematic errors in how people process information, known as cognitive distortions. These distortions, rooted in negatively processed information, encompass three key elements. First, they involve thoughts that hinder individuals from achieving their goals. Second, they entail unrealistic expectations of

themselves, others, and the world. Lastly, they involve an exaggerated, negative assessment of events (Kirchner et al., 2023).

The concept of cognitive distortions can also manifest in context of interpersonal relationships. The cognitive distortions related to interpersonal relationships are termed as interpersonal cognitive distortions (Hamamcı, 2002). These distortions affect how individuals perceive and interact with others. Interpersonal cognitive distortions involve incorrect and biased ways of interpreting social interactions and the behaviors of others. These distorted thinking errors can lead to misunderstandings, conflicts, and maladaptive behaviors in relationships (Kirchner et al., 2023). These distortions can arise from early maladaptive schemas formed through past experiences which then influence adult relationships (Hamamcı, 2002).

Types of Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions

As conceptualized by Hamamcı (2004), interpersonal cognitive distortions can be categorized into three primary types: intimacy avoidance (or interpersonal rejection), unrealistic relationship expectations, and interpersonal misperception (or mind reading). Each category reflects distinct patterns of distorted thinking that significantly impact how individuals perceive and interact within their interpersonal relationships.

Intimacy Avoidance

Interpersonal rejection, or intimacy avoidance, includes the negative thoughts revolving around the intense fear of closeness and negative attitudes toward others. It further leads to the avoidance of intimate relationships. Individuals with this cognitive distortion often believe that forming close bonds will certainly lead to negative outcomes (Kirchner et al., 2023). This cognitive distortion involves many negative thoughts, for instance, the certainty that intimacy will result in abandonment, and the perception that any conflict prevents true intimacy etc. These

beliefs and thinking patterns create a defensive barrier against intimacy, often leading individuals to self-sabotage potential close relationships (Hamamcı, 2002).

Unrealistic Relationship Expectations

Unrealistic relationship expectations include overly high and often unattainable standards for both oneself and others within relationships. Individuals having this cognitive distortion believe that others should always be understanding, supportive, and meet their emotional needs unconditionally. They might expect constant companionship and feel a constant need to belong to a social group (Kashaninia et al., 2022). They interpret the fulfillment of these needs as essential for their well-being. This can lead to significant disappointment and frustration when reality fails to meet these idealized standards. This distortion can lead to a cycle of dependency and dissatisfaction, as the gap between expectations and reality becomes distressful (Hamamcı, 2002).

Interpersonal Misperception

Interpersonal misperception, or mind reading, involves the irrational belief that one can accurately understand others' thoughts and feelings without open communication. This distortion is characterized by assumptions that one's interpretations of others' non-verbal cues are always accurate (Kashaninia et al., 2022). This can lead to significant misunderstandings and conflicts, as the perceptions are often inaccurate (Hamamcı, 2002).

Beck's Cognitive Model Explaining Cognitive Distortions

Beck's cognitive model provides a comprehensive theoretical framework for understanding the cognitive processes underlying psychopathology. It describes how cognitive and behavioral processes contribute to the development of various psychological disorders. The central idea of Beck's cognitive model is that everyday psychological problems and clinical

disorders represent exaggerated forms of normal adaptive functioning. The model suggests that typical information processing involves biases. He theorized that negative biases exaggerate threats or challenges, while positive biases amplify perceived rewards. However, these biases can lead to maladaptive functioning and psychological disorders when are excessively pronounced (Beck & Beck, 2011). He defined cognitive schemas as mentally stored representations of stimuli, ideas, or experiences, which play an important role in this process. These schemas control information processing systems which range from lower-order automatic processing to higher-order reflective processing. Whenever a schema is activated after a stimulus or a trigger, it generates specific meanings that interact with cognitive, affective, motivational, and behavioral systems. Beck suggests that cognitive biases can be either conditional or absolute and they exist on a spectrum from adaptive to maladaptive. When the cognitive bias exceeds a certain adaptive threshold, it significantly increases the likelihood of an individual experiencing subclinical or clinical disorders (Beck & Beck, 2011).

Beck's cognitive model can also be applicable in explaining how exaggerated interpersonal cognitive biases can impair interpersonal relationships. Interpersonal cognitive distortions, such as intimacy avoidance, unrealistic relationship expectations, and mind reading, originate from maladaptive schemas. The early maladaptive schemas distort how individuals perceive and interact with others (Kashaninia et al., 2022). These schemas are activated by social stimuli and produce biased beliefs that skew information processing. It then leads to misinterpretations of social cues and interactions (Beck, 2011).

Previous Research Related to Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions

Previous research on interpersonal cognitive distortions has been done associating it with various psychological and social outcomes. Şimşek et al. (2021) emphasized the role of

loneliness as a mediator between interpersonal cognitive distortions and life satisfaction, specifically highlighting the impact of loneliness on young individuals' life satisfaction. This association between loneliness and interpersonal cognitive distortion provides a basis for understanding the implications of cognitive distortions on emotional well-being.

Kirchner et al. (2023) extended this understanding by validating the Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions Scale. The findings on the scale's psychometric properties suggest that loneliness and insecurity could be linked with interpersonal cognitive distortions. It further complicates the individual's psychological wellbeing. The validation of the interpersonal cognitive distortions scale also fills the gap between theoretical constructs and practical applications. Kaya et al. (2023) showed that interpersonal cognitive distortions partially mediate the relationship between attachment anxiety and interpersonal relationship styles. This mediating role suggests that attachment-related anxieties could intensify loneliness and insecurity, which further reinforce cognitive distortions.

The relationship between self-perception and interpersonal cognitive distortions is further explained by Akın (2010), who identified self-compassion as a significant predictor of interpersonal cognitive distortions. Negative self-perception, self-judgment and isolation are positively correlated with interpersonal cognitive distortions. On the other hand, it was found that fostering self-kindness, humanity, and mindfulness could moderate these distortions. Akın's work suggests that improving self-compassion may serve as a barrier against the adverse effects of interpersonal cognitive distortions. It resonates with the intervention strategies implied by Şimşek et al. (2012). They introduced the behavioral dimension by linking interpersonal cognitive distortions to problematic internet use among university students. It was found that over-thinking was negatively correlated with decision-making skills. This suggests interpersonal

cognitive distortions impair decision-making and lead to maladaptive behaviors like excessive internet use. Çelebi and Kaya (2022) identified that emotional intelligence was a partial mediator between interpersonal cognitive distortions and anxiety. Their findings imply that higher emotional intelligence can alleviate the anxiety-inducing effects of interpersonal cognitive distortions. The significant correlation between interpersonal dependency and interpersonal cognitive distortions was found by Çayır and Kalkan (2018). They suggested that interpersonal dependency could be seen as both a cause and consequence of heightened ICDs which suggests a feedback loop where dependency reinforces cognitive distortions and vice versa.

Bozkur and Gündoğdu (2018) added a sociocultural perspective by examining the impact of ambivalent sexism and maternal bonding on ICDs. They found that sexism and maternal bonding significantly predict ICDs. They suggest that early socialization and gender norms shape cognitive distortions. Lastly, Aydın and Akgün (2021) highlighted the practical implications of ICDs during the COVID-19 pandemic, where heightened interpersonal cognitive distortions were linked to task and relationship performance in family roles. This situational context underlines the pervasive impact of ICDs across various life domains, particularly under stress, and connects back to the broader themes of emotional well-being and interpersonal dynamics discussed throughout the literature.

Limerence

Tennov (1979), introduced the concept of limerence as a distinct mental state associated with romantic love, explaining its characteristics in her book "Love and Limerence: The Experience of Being in Love". Tennov identified a common set of symptoms during the initial stages of falling in love, through extensive interviews with individuals in romantic relationships. These symptoms include frequent intrusive thoughts about the limerent object (LO), an acute

desire for reciprocation, exaggerated mood dependency on the LO's actions, inability to react limerently to multiple individuals simultaneously, temporary relief through vivid fantasies, insecurity or shyness in the LO's presence often accompanied by physical discomfort, amplification of feelings amidst adversity, aching sensation in the heart during uncertainty, intense emotional focus overshadowing other concerns, and a notable tendency to accentuate positive traits while downplaying or empathizing with negative ones in the LO.

Limerence and other Love States

According to Wolf (2017) and others, the term 'passionate love' has been used extensively as a synonymous term for 'Limerence'. However, although the terms 'limerence' and 'passionate love' are both intense emotional states and they may seem to be similar, some aspects of limerence make it unique from passionate love. Limerence is a specific term used to describe an intense infatuation or romantic attraction, commonly associated with obsession and longing for reciprocation, whereas passionate love refers to a broader state of intense emotional and physical attraction, often accompanied by excitement and desire.

Sternberg (1986) proposed that by combining the three fundamental elements of love i.e., 'intimacy', 'passion', and 'decision/commitment', eight distinct types of love relationships emerge. For instance, those relationships which are mainly infatuation based, have relatively low levels of commitment and intimacy but have relatively high levels of passion. Similarly, relationships based on merely liking, have relatively high level of intimacy but low levels of passion and commitment.

Blue Angel Syndrome

The Blue Angel Syndrome describes a phenomenon where individuals exhibit pathological infatuation, often leading to repeated self-destructive behavior. This behavior

typically involves sacrificing one's own well-being and interests for the sake of the object of their affection. Whereas limerence encompasses a range of emotional experiences, including idealization of the partner alongside heightened emotional intensity. The Blue Angel Syndrome specifically denotes a pattern of behavior marked by detrimental consequences and a lack of regard for one's own welfare. It also highlights the maladaptive and self-destructive behaviors that may accompany extreme infatuation. Whereas limerence on the other hand, focuses on the emotional and cognitive aspects of romantic attachment.

Development of Limerence

According to Tennov (1979) there are three key factors that are essential for limerence to develop into a transformative obsession namely 'The Glimmer', 'The Response', and 'Uncertainty'.

The Glimmer

Limerence begins with a distinct attraction, described as "the glimmer," where certain individuals evoke strong emotional and physiological responses. It transcends simple attraction, involving a deep personal connection that triggers intense arousal and heightened awareness. This initial spark is crucial and often recognized subconsciously soon after meeting a potential romantic interest.

The Response

Following the glimmer, the limerent individual becomes hyperaware of the potential reciprocation from their object of affection (LO). Each interaction is scrutinized for signs of interest or disinterest, which can either fuel or inhibit the progression of limerence. Small signs of reciprocation are often magnified, while uncertainty about the LO's feelings intensifies the desire for reciprocation.

Uncertainty

Uncertainty acts as a potent catalyst for deepening limerent feelings. It fuels obsessive analysis of interactions, encourages fantasizing about potential scenarios, and increases fixation on the LO. Mixed signals and external barriers, such as existing relationships or social constraints, contribute to uncertainty and further amplify limerent emotions. Despite obstacles, the possibility of reciprocation keeps the limerent hope alive, perpetuating the cycle of desire and fixation.

Phases of Limerence

Tennov (1979) characterized Limerence into three phases i.e., ‘The Infatuation Phase’, ‘Addiction Phase’ and ‘The Recovery Phase’.

Infatuation Phase

This initial stage is characterized by euphoria as one becomes increasingly attracted to their LO. Sharing intimacies and anticipating future interactions contribute to idealizing and admiring them. Neurologically, this phase is marked by the enjoyment of rewarding experiences.

Addiction Phase

In this stage, the obsession with the LO is deeply entrenched. They dominate one’s thoughts, leading to intrusive and persistent rumination. One may neglect other responsibilities and relationships as they devote significant time and energy to deciphering the feelings of their LO. Mood swings are common, heavily influenced by the behavior of the LO.

Recovery Phase

As the intensity of limerence wanes, perspective begins to return. One’s perception of the LO shifts, recognizing their flaws and humanity. This phase may be accompanied by feelings of regret or remorse, particularly if one’s actions during the addiction phase harmed other

relationships. Recovery involves extinguishing the habitual seeking of the LO. The duration of each phase varies among individuals and is influenced by both personal psychology and the behavior of the LO.

Biological Basis of Limerence

Understanding limerence from a neurobiological perspective reveals the intricate workings of the brain and its chemical messengers. Neuroscientists claim that such profound shifts in mood and behavior stem from the intricate mechanisms within the brain. Limerence manifests as a rollercoaster of emotions, where individuals are captivated by a new romantic interest, leading to heightened perceptions and intense emotional responses. This phenomenon is driven by three primary neurochemical systems: reward, arousal, and bonding.

Dopamine fuels the euphoric highs associated with limerence, while noradrenaline heightens alertness and arousal, amplifying emotional responses. Oxytocin and vasopressin facilitate emotional bonding, fostering a sense of closeness and contentment. These neural systems form a self-reinforcing cycle, triggering a deepening desire and ultimately culminating in a craving for the limerent object. The parallels between limerence and addiction are striking, with similar neural pathways and behavioral patterns observed. Just as with substance addiction, limerence progresses from initial exhilaration to dependency, disrupting everyday life and compelling individuals to prioritize their limerent object above all else (Tennov, 1979) .

Therapeutic Treatment Options for Limerence

Treating limerence involves an eclectic approach using various modalities to address its multifaceted symptoms. Trauma-focused therapy is an essential part of treatment, providing ways for people to address and overcome childhood traumas and related experiences. At the same time, Dialectical Behavior Therapy (DBT) intervenes with a focus on enhancing

interpersonal skills, managing emotions better, and develop mindfulness. These components work collectively to teach individuals how they can navigate intense emotional states and interpersonal dynamics associated with limerence. Like DBT, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) targets cognitive distortions and behavioral patterns, as well as provide strategies to challenge and reframe maladaptive thoughts and actions. Additionally, Schema Therapy offers a deeper exploration of entrenched maladaptive schemas, such as abandonment, rejection, and failure, providing a framework for understanding and restructuring deeply ingrained beliefs. Through this integrated approach, individuals engage in a comprehensive therapeutic journey aimed at untangling the complex web of emotions, thoughts, and behaviors characteristic of limerence, ultimately fostering greater self-awareness, emotional resilience, and relational health.

Objectives of the Study

The current research addresses the following objectives.

1. To explore the relationship between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, interpersonal misperception and limerence among young adults.
2. To explore the gender differences in terms of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence among young adults.
3. To check whether there is a difference in fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence among young adults with different relationship statuses.
4. To check whether interpersonal cognitive distortions have a mediating effect on the relationship of fear of abandonment and limerence.
5. To check whether intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, interpersonal misperception have mediating effects on the relationship of fear of abandonment and limerence.

Hypotheses of the Study

H1: There is a relationship between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, interpersonal misperception and limerence among young adults.

H2: There are gender differences in fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence among young men and women.

H3: There is a difference in fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence among young adults with different relationship statuses.

H4: Interpersonal cognitive distortions have a mediating effect in the relationship of fear of abandonment and limerence among young adults.

H5: Intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, and interpersonal misperception have mediating effects in the relationship of fear of abandonment and limerence among young adults.

Chapter III

Methods

Research Method

In this research, to investigate the relationship between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence, a correlational research design was used.

Research Participants

A sample size of 330 was determined using G-Power analysis. The effect size was 0.15 with the alpha error of 0.05. Purposive sampling was used, and a sample of 340 participants was recruited from different private and public universities of Lahore, Pakistan. Out of 340 participants, eight of them made errors in filling in the questionnaires, so they were eliminated. Only eligible participants were selected who fulfilled the inclusion criteria of the research, to maintain the homogeneity of the participants' characteristics. The inclusion criteria of the research were young adult participants with the age range of 18 to 29 years studying in a public or private university of Lahore.

Measurement Tools

Following reliable and validated measurement tools were used in this research to collect data from the participants.

Socio-Demographic Questionnaire

To collect information related to demographics of participants a socio-demographic questionnaire was constructed in English language. It included the variables age, gender, relationship status, education level, and majors. Gender had three categories including men, women and others. Relationship status had four categories including people who have never been in a relationship, people who are currently single and had a history of at least one romantic

relationship breakup, people who were in a romantic relationship, and people who were in a complicated, uncertain relationship often termed as casual, complicated relationship or situationship. Education level included bachelors, masters, and doctorate. Lastly, majors included four categories i.e. Business, Humanities, Natural Sciences, Social Sciences.

Abandonment Core Belief Self-Assessment (Skeen, 2014)

Abandonment Core Belief Self-Assessment is an adaptation of Young's schema questionnaire (Young et al., 2003). It is used to evaluate an individual's belief that the important people in their life will be unable to provide emotional support, either due to their own emotional instability, death, or leaving the person for someone else. It was adapted by Skeen (2014). It is a self-report 10 items scale. The questionnaire uses a six-point Likert-type scale, which ranges from 1 (completely untrue of me) to 6 (describes me perfectly). The scale has satisfactory psychometric properties.

Wolf & Lemay Limerence Measure (WLLM; Wolf & Lemay, 2015)

The limerence measure is a self-report assessment tool used to measure the symptoms of limerence in an individual. It was developed by Wolf and Lemay (2015). It is the only assessment tool available which measures limerence. It consists of 30 items. The scale uses a 7-point Likert-type scale, which ranges from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). The scale measures limerence on seven core symptoms namely, exclusivity, uncertainty, idealization, intrusive thinking, ache in chest, elation and inability to become non-limerent. The scale has significant psychometric properties. The reliability coefficient was Cronbach's $\alpha = .89$.

Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions Scale (ICDS; Hamamci, 2004)

The Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions Scale evaluates cognitive distortions in individuals who are in any kind of personal relationship. It was developed by (Hamamci, 2004).

It consists of 19 items. The measure uses a 5-point Likert-type scale, which ranges from 1 (I strongly disagree) to 5 (I strongly agree). High scores on a particular sub domain indicate a high level of cognitive distortion in personal relationships. The scale includes three subscales; avoidance of intimacy also termed as interpersonal rejection consisted of 8 items, unrealistic relationship expectations subscale contained 8 items, and lastly interpersonal misperception also termed as mind reading sub domain consisted of 3 items. Total scores on the scale can range from a minimum of 19 to a maximum of 95. The measure demonstrates strong psychometric properties with Cronbach's alpha of .89.

Study Procedure

Firstly, permission to conduct this study was taken from the Board of Studies, and Ethical Review Committee under the reference number ERC Ref: PSYC699-23-121 at Department of Psychology, FCCU. The approved proposal was then submitted to Institutional Review Board, FCCU and permission was taken under the reference number Ref: IRB-569/01-2024. After getting the permissions from institutional authorities, the permission to use tools was taken from the relevant authors of the measurement tools by writing them emails. After getting permissions from the authors a booklet was made including consent form, socio-demographic questionnaire, and the measurement tools. To collect data from different public and private universities in Lahore, permission was taken by writing emails, submitting formal letters from the Department of Psychology, FCCU along with the booklet to the relevant authorities of the institutes. After getting permissions from institutes, the participants were recruited from their academic institutions using purposive sampling strategy.

On reaching the sample, the aim and objectives of the research were explained to the participants before they filled out the booklets. They were made certain about their voluntary

participation, confidentiality of the information provided by them, and their right to withdraw anytime they feel threatened or uncomfortable while filling the booklet. Their queries were answered. After that, the research participants were given a booklet containing an informed consent, instructions, a socio-demographic questionnaire, and measurement tools. Additionally, along with written instructions to fill the booklet, verbal instructions were also given to the participants. They were instructed to read each item carefully and select the options that best reflected their feelings or thoughts, as there are no right or wrong answers. Upon completing the booklet, participants were thanked for their cooperation and participation in the research.

Ethical Considerations

The permission for conducting this research was taken from the BOS, ERC and then IRB. Permission to use the tools in the study was obtained by emailing the relevant authors of the scales. Before completing the questionnaires, both verbal and written consent was obtained from the participants regarding their participation in the study. Moreover, the confidentiality of the information given by participants was assured. Only those individuals were recruited who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. Anonymity and confidentiality of the participants was strictly ensured by assigning codes to booklets randomly after data collection. The collected data was only accessible to the main researcher and the supervisor. No participant was harmed in any way during the research. The results and findings were reported accurately.

Statistical Analysis

Following data collection, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0 was used to analyze the gathered data. Descriptive statistics were used to assess the socio-demographic profile of the sample. Descriptive statistics included calculating the frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations of socio demographic variables including ae,

gender, relationship status, education level and majors. For inferential statistics, various statistical analyses were used according to the sample distribution and formulated hypotheses. For instance, reliability analysis was used to check the reliability of measurement tools in this sample, tests of normality were done to check the normal distribution. Pearson product-moment correlation analysis was used to check the relationship between the study variables; fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence. One Way-Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was used to check the gender differences and differences in relationship status groups in terms of study variables. Furthermore, mediation analyses using PROCESS Macro was utilized to check the mediating effect of interpersonal cognitive distortions and its sub domains in the relationship of fear of abandonment and limerence. All the results including interpretations, tables, and figures were reported using APA 7 manual format.

Chapter IV

Results

This research aimed at investigating how interpersonal cognitive distortions mediate the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence along with the moderating effect of gender and relationship status. For this purpose, a correlational research design was employed, and data was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS v26). This research includes one independent variable (fear of abandonment) measured on Abandonment Core Belief Self-Assessment (Skeen, 2014), one mediator (interpersonal cognitive distortions) with three subscales (Interpersonal misperception, unrealistic relationship expectations, and intimacy avoidance) which also served as independent variables measured on Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions Scale (Hamamcı, 2004), one dependent variable (limerence) measured on Wolf & Lemay Limerence Measure (Wolf & Lemay, 2015). In this chapter, the results are discussed in detail. This chapter is divided into five sections i.e, demographic profile of the sample, testing of the main hypotheses, relationship between demographic variables and research variables.

Section I: Demographic profile of the sample

Section II: Testing of the main hypotheses

Section III: Summary of Results

Section I: Demographic Profile of the Sample

This section of the results chapter includes description of sample and their demographic profile ($N=332$)

Table 1

Table Showing Demographic Profile of Sample (N=332)

Variables	<i>f</i>	(%)	<i>M (SD)</i>
Age of Participants			21.8 (2.05)
Gender			
Men	153	46.1%	
Women	179	53.9%	
Relationship Status			
Never Been in a Relationship	87	26.2%	
Currently Single/Broken up	79	23.8%	
In a Relationship	84	25.3%	
Situationship	82	24.7%	
Education Level			
Bachelors	255	76.8%	
Masters	77	23.2%	
Major Discipline			
Business	65	19.6%	
Humanities	47	14.2%	
Natural Sciences	87	26.2%	
Social Sciences	133	40.1%	

Note. *f*= Frequency; %= Percentage; *M*= Mean; *SD*= Standard Deviation

Table 1 shows frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation of participants' demographic variables $N=332$. The mean age of participants was 21.8 years ($SD = 2.05$). The gender distribution showed a slightly high proportion of women, with 53.9% ($f = 179$) compared to men (46.1%, $f = 153$). In terms of relationship status, participants were relatively evenly distributed: 26.2% ($f = 87$) had never been in a relationship, 23.8% ($f = 79$) were currently single or had broken up, 25.3% ($f = 84$) were in a relationship, and 24.7% ($f = 82$) were in a complicated relationship i.e, situationship. Regarding education level, most of the participants were doing a bachelor's degree (76.8%, $f = 255$), while 23.2% ($f = 77$) were doing a master's

degree. The distribution of major disciplines revealed that most of the participants were from the Social Sciences (40.1%, $f = 133$), followed by Natural Sciences (26.2%, $f = 87$), Business (19.6%, $f = 65$), and Humanities (14.2%, $f = 47$).

Table 2

Mean, and Standard Deviation of Study Variables (N=332)

Variables	Total Sample		Men (N=153)		Women (N=179)		Cohen's <i>d</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	
Fear of Abandonment	32.18	12.1	25.4	9.6	37.96	10.9	1.22
Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions	54.94	12.9	49.6	12.4	59.5	11.5	0.83
Intimacy Avoidance	22.61	6.1	20.4	5.9	24.5	5.7	0.71
Unrealistic Expectations	23.64	6.6	21.3	6.6	25.6	5.9	0.69
Interpersonal Misperception	8.69	2.3	7.9	2.9	9.4	2.9	0.52
Limerence	125.5	37.3	97.3	29.1	149.6	24.3	1.96

Note. *M*= Mean; *SD*= Standard Deviation

Table 2 shows an overview of the mean *M* and standard deviation *SD* of study variables for total sample $N=332$, men $N=153$ and women $N=179$ separately. Fear of Abandonment shows a significant gender difference. The mean score for the total sample is ($M=32.18$, $SD = 12.1$). However, men report a significantly lower mean ($M = 25.4$, $SD = 9.6$) compared to women ($M = 37.96$, $SD = 10.9$), with Cohen's $d = 1.22$ indicating a large effect size. This suggests that women experience a significantly higher fear of abandonment than men. For Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions, the total sample mean is $M=54.94$, $SD = 12.9$. However, men report lower mean ($M=49.6$, $SD = 12.4$), whereas women report higher mean ($M=59.5$, $SD = 11.5$). The Cohen's d value of 0.83 suggests a large effect size, indicating that women are more prone to interpersonal cognitive distortions than men. The subscales of interpersonal cognitive distortions were analysed separately, and it was found that means and standard deviations of subscale 1 (Intimacy

Avoidance) also exhibits gender differences, though to a slightly lesser extent. The mean for the total sample is $M=22.61$, $SD = 6.1$. Men have a mean of $M=20.4$, $SD = 5.9$, while women have a higher mean of $M=24.5$, $SD = 5.7$. The effect size, with Cohen's $d = 0.71$, indicates a moderate to large difference, suggesting women tend to avoid intimacy more than men.

The mean and standard deviations of subscale 2 (Unrealistic Expectations) were analysed and it was found that the total sample mean is $M=23.64$, $SD = 6.6$. Men score lower ($M = 21.3$, $SD = 6.6$) compared to women ($M = 25.6$, $SD = 5.9$). The effect size was moderate to large Cohen's $d = 0.69$, implying that women hold more unrealistic expectations in relationships than men. The mean score for subscale 3 (Interpersonal Misperception) in the total sample was $M=8.69$, $SD = 2.3$. Men have a mean of $M=7.9$, $SD = 2.9$, while women score higher with a mean of $M=9.4$, $SD = 2.9$. The Cohen's d value of 0.52 indicates a moderate effect size, reflecting that women are more likely to misperceive interpersonal interactions than men.

Limerence showed the most significant gender difference among all study variables. The total sample mean was $M=125.5$, $SD = 37.3$. Men have a significantly lower mean ($M = 97.3$, $SD = 29.1$) compared to women ($M = 149.6$, $SD = 24.3$). The Cohen's d value of 1.96 suggests a very large effect size, indicating that women experience limerence to a much greater extent than men.

Reliability Analysis

Table 3

Cronbach α Values of Measurement Tools, their Subscales and No. of Items (N=332)

Scale Name	Cronbach's Alpha α	Number of Items
Young Schema Questionnaire- Abandonment	0.88	10
Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions Scale	0.85	19
Intimacy Avoidance	0.75	8

Unrealistic Expectations	0.72	8
Interpersonal Misperception	0.65	3
Wolf & Lemay Limerence Measure	0.94	30
Exclusivity	0.90	4
Intrusive Thinking	0.94	4
Uncertainty	0.89	4
Idealization	0.84	4
Ache in Chest	0.92	4
Elation	0.91	3
Apprehension	0.82	3
Inability to Become Non-limerent	0.93	4

Table 3 shows the reliability analysis of the measurement tools and their subscales used in the study using Cronbach's alpha (α). The Abandonment Core Belief Self-Assessment showed a high level of internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.88 across its 10 items. The Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions Scale and its subscales demonstrated varying levels of reliability: the overall scale had a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85 with 19 items, while the subscales intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, and interpersonal misperception had alphas of 0.75, 0.72, and 0.65, respectively. The Wolf & Lemay Limerence Measure and its subdomains indicated excellent reliability, with the overall scale achieving a Cronbach's alpha of 0.94 across 30 items. The subscales including exclusivity, intrusive thinking, uncertainty, idealization, ache in chest, elation, apprehension, and inability to become non-limerent had Cronbach's alphas ranging from 0.82 to 0.94, indicating strong internal consistency. These results suggest that the measurement tools possess good to excellent reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values exceeding the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70.

Section II: Testing of the Main Hypotheses

This section of chapter IV includes the main statistical analyses used to test the study's hypotheses. The rationale for using a particular statistical analysis is also given with each analysis.

Relationship of Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions, Intimacy Avoidance, Unrealistic Expectations, Interpersonal Misperception and Limerence

The first hypothesis was about the association between independent variables i.e, fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions including intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, interpersonal misperception and the dependent variable i.e, limerence. The hypothesis formulated to access this relationship is as follows.

H1: There is a significant relationship between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, interpersonal misperception and limerence among young adults.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to assess the strength and direction of the relationships between these variables because it quantifies the degree to which the study variables are linearly associated. Other analyses, such as Spearman's rank-order correlation or Kendall's tau, were not used because these are more suitable for ordinal data or for data that do not meet the assumptions of normality and linearity.

Table 4

<i>Pearson Product Moment Correlations Between Study Variables (N=332)</i>									
Variables	<i>N</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Abandonment	332	32.18	12.1	-	0.66**	0.65**	0.62**	0.54**	0.38**
2. ICD	332	125.5	37.3		-	0.56**	0.85**	0.86**	0.65**
3. Limerence	332	54.94	12.9			-	0.48**	0.48**	0.35**
4. IA	332	22.61	6.1				-	0.54**	0.44**
5. UE	332	23.64	6.6					-	0.40**
6. IM	332	8.69	2.3						-

Note. ** $p < 0.01$; *M*= Mean; *SD*= Standard Deviation; *ICD*=Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions; *IA*= Intimacy Avoidance; *UE*= Unrealistic Expectations; *IM*= Interpersonal Misperception

Table 4 shows a summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation used to analyze the relationships among study variables in a sample of $N=332$ young adults. The results showed that fear of abandonment has a significant strong positive relationship with interpersonal cognitive distortions ($r=0.66$, $p < 0.01$), intimacy avoidance ($r = 0.62$, $p < 0.01$), and limerence ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.01$). This indicates that individuals with higher levels of fear of abandonment will have greater interpersonal cognitive distortions, they are more likely to avoid intimacy and they tend to experience more limerence. There was a significant moderate to strong positive relationship between fear of abandonment and unrealistic expectations ($r = 0.54$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that higher fear of abandonment is associated with more unrealistic expectations in interpersonal relationships. The correlation between fear of abandonment and interpersonal misperception was ($r = 0.38$, $p < 0.01$), indicating a significant moderate positive relationship.

Furthermore, it was found that interpersonal cognitive distortions have a significant strong, positive relationship with limerence ($r = 0.56$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that individuals with more interpersonal cognitive distortions tend to experience more limerence. There was a significant very strong positive correlation between interpersonal cognitive distortions and its

sub-domains i.e, intimacy avoidance ($r = 0.85$, $p < 0.01$), unrealistic expectations ($r = 0.86$, $p < 0.01$), and significant strong positive correlation with interpersonal misperception ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.01$). Moreover, limerence has a significant moderate to strong positive relationship with intimacy avoidance ($r = 0.48$, $p < 0.01$), unrealistic expectations ($r = 0.48$, $p < 0.01$) and a significant moderate positive relationship with interpersonal misperception ($r = 0.35$, $p < 0.01$).

Conclusion. In conclusion, the results support the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, interpersonal misperception, and limerence among young adults.

Gender Differences in Terms of Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions and Limerence

The second hypothesis was about the gender differences in terms of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence. The hypothesis formulated to access this relationship is as follows.

H2: There are gender differences in terms of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence among young men and women.

One-Way Multivariate Analysis of Variance was used to assess the differences among two groups men and women in terms of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence. This analysis is suitable as it allows for the simultaneous comparison of multiple dependent variables (fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence) across the two gender groups (men and women), thereby reducing the risk of Type I error that could arise from conducting multiple univariate tests. Other analyses, such as multiple

ANOVAs, would not account for the intercorrelations among the dependent variables and could increase the likelihood of Type I errors.

Table 5

Table showing gender differences in terms of study variables N=332

Dependent Variables	Men (N=153)		Women (N=179)		η^2	p	F
	M	SD	M	SD			
FOA	25.4	9.6	37.96	10.9	0.27	0.000	122.05
ICD	49.6	12.4	59.5	11.5	0.15	0.000	57.14
Limerence	97.3	29.1	149.6	24.3	0.49	0.000	318.10

Note. p < .001, M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; FOA = Fear of Abandonment,*

ICD = Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions; η^2 = Partial Eta Squared.

Table 5 shows the results of the one-way MANOVA conducted to explore gender differences in fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence among young men and women. Descriptive statistics indicate that women reported higher mean scores than men across all three dependent variables: fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence. The multivariate tests show a significant effect of gender on the combined dependent variables, Wilks' Lambda = .499, $F(3, 328) = 109.653$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .501$. This suggests that approximately 50.1% of the variance in the dependent variables is accounted for by gender differences.

The results revealed significant gender differences for fear of abandonment as $F(1, 330) = 122.050$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .270$. This indicates a significant effect size, with 27% of the variance in fear of abandonment explained by gender. The gender differences for interpersonal cognitive distortions were significant as $F(1, 330) = 57.136$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .148$. It indicates that gender accounts for 14.8% of the variance in interpersonal cognitive distortions.

The gender differences for limerence were significant as $F(1, 330) = 318.104, p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .491$, indicating 49.1% of the variance in limerence scores is attributable to gender.

Post hoc pairwise comparisons using the Bonferroni adjustment showed that women scored significantly higher than men in fear of abandonment with a significant mean difference of -12.543 (SE = 1.135, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-14.776, -10.309]). Women scored significantly higher than men for interpersonal cognitive distortions, with a mean difference of -9.901 (SE = 1.310, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-12.477, -7.324]). Lastly women scoring significantly higher than men by -52.294 (SE = 2.932, $p < .001$, 95% CI [-58.062, -46.526]).

Conclusion. The results indicates that there are significant gender differences in fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence among young men and women and the hypothesis was proved.

Differences in Relationship Status in Terms of Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions and Limerence

The third hypothesis was related to check the differences among different relationship status groups i.e, people who were never in a relationship, currently single, in a relationship and in situationship. The hypothesis formulated to check these differences is as follows.

H3: There is a difference in fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence among young adults with different relationship statuses.

One-Way Multivariate Analysis of Variance was used to assess the differences among four groups i.e, never been in a relationship, currently single, in a relationship and in situationship, in terms of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence. This analysis is suitable as it allows for the simultaneous comparison of multiple dependent variables (fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence) across the four

groups of relationship status, thereby reducing the risk of Type I error that could arise from conducting multiple univariate tests.

Table 6

Table showing differences in relationship status in terms of study variables (N=332)

Dependent Variables	Never in a Relationship (N=87)		Currently Single (N=79)		In a Relationship (N=84)		In a Complicated Relationship / Situationship (N=82)		η^2	p	F
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
	FOA	23.1	8.2	30.6	9.4	36.9	11.9	38.3			
ICD	46.8	11.7	54.3	10.7	57.9	11.9	61.1	12.4	0.18	0.000	23.59
Limerence	82.2	27.1	127.3	18.8	142.7	22.9	152.1	31.4	0.53	0.000	125.57

Note. $p^* < .001$, M= Mean; SD= Standard Deviation; FOA= Fear of Abandonment,

ICD=Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions; η^2 = Partial Eta Squared.

Table 6 shows the results of the One-Way MANOVA conducted to explore the differences in fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence among young adults with different relationship statuses including never been in a relationship, currently single with a breakup history, in a relationship, and in a complicated relationship /situationship). The multivariate tests show a significant effect of relationship status on the combined dependent variables. Pillai's Trace = 0.554, $F(9, 984) = 24.781$, $p < .001$; Wilks' Lambda = .456, $F(9, 793.549) = 33.585$, $p < .001$; Hotelling's Trace = 1.171, $F(9, 974) = 42.244$, $p < .001$; Roy's Largest Root = 1.152, $F(3, 328) = 125.920$, $p < .001$) show significant results with p-values less than .001, which indicates that there are overall differences in fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence across different relationship statuses. The partial eta squared values (Pillai's Trace $\eta^2 = .185$, Wilks' Lambda $\eta^2 = .230$, Hotelling's Trace $\eta^2 = .281$, Roy's Largest Root $\eta^2 = .535$) indicate significant multivariate effect sizes. The results indicate significant differences in fear of abandonment ($F(3, 328) = 37.382$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .255$),

interpersonal cognitive distortions ($F(3, 328) = 23.599, p < .001, \eta^2 = .178$), and limerence ($F(3, 328) = 125.568, p < .001, \eta^2 = .535$) among the different relationship statuses.

Post hoc comparisons using the Bonferroni correction show significant pairwise differences for fear of abandonment as individuals who were never been in a relationship reported significantly lower fear of abandonment ($M = 23.18, SD = 8.23$) as compared to those who are currently single ($M = 30.63, SD = 9.42, p < .001$), in a relationship ($M = 36.94, SD = 11.89, p < .001$), and in a complicated relationship or situationship ($M = 38.34, SD = 11.83, p < .001$). Those who are currently single reported lower fear of abandonment scores as compared to those in a relationship ($p < .001$) and those in a complicated relationship or situationship ($p < .001$). However, there was no significant difference found in fear of abandonment between those in a relationship and those in a complicated relationship or situationship ($p = .388$).

Post hoc comparisons using the Bonferroni correction also revealed that individuals who have never been in a relationship reported significantly lower interpersonal cognitive distortions ($M = 46.80, SD = 11.70$) as compared to those who are currently single and had a breakup history ($M = 54.28, SD = 10.74, p < .001$), in a relationship ($M = 57.93, SD = 11.90, p < .001$), and in a complicated relationship or situationship ($M = 61.17, SD = 12.44, p < .001$). Those currently single reported lower interpersonal cognitive distortions compared to those in a complicated relationship or situationship ($p < .001$). However, a significant difference was found between those who are currently single and those in a relationship ($p = .048$), but no significant difference was found between those in a relationship and those in a complicated relationship or situationship ($p = .076$).

Lastly, Post hoc comparisons using the Bonferroni correction showed that individuals who have never been in a relationship reported significantly lower limerence ($M = 82.28, SD =$

27.06) compared to those who are currently single and had a breakup history ($M = 127.25$, $SD = 18.76$, $p < .001$), in a relationship ($M = 142.71$, $SD = 22.90$, $p < .001$), and in a complicated relationship or situationship ($M = 152.10$, $SD = 31.42$, $p < .001$). The results also revealed that those who are currently single reported lower limerence as compared to those in a relationship ($p < .001$) and in a complicated relationship or situationship ($p < .001$). Those in a relationship reported lower limerence as compared to those in a situationship ($p = .019$).

Conclusion. The results indicate that relationship status significantly affects levels of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence among young adults. Particularly, individuals who have never been in a relationship exhibit the lowest levels of these variables. Those who were in complicated relationships or situationships have the highest levels of these variables. Thus, the results support the hypothesis that there is a significant difference in individual's scores on fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence with different relationship statuses.

Interpersonal Cognitive Distortion as Mediator in the Relationship of Fear of Abandonment and Limerence

The fourth hypothesis was formulated to check whether interpersonal cognitive distortions play a mediating role in the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence. The hypothesis formulated is as follow.

H4: Interpersonal cognitive distortions play a mediating role in the relationship of fear of abandonment and limerence among young adults.

Mediation Analysis Using PROCESS Macro was utilised to check this hypothesis because it allows to explore how fear of abandonment influences limerence by introducing interpersonal cognitive distortions as an intermediary variable. Unlike other analytical

techniques, mediation analysis can partition the total effect into direct and indirect effects, providing a nuanced understanding of both the direct impact of fear of abandonment on limerence and the indirect impact mediated by cognitive distortions.

Table 7

Mediating Effect of Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions in the Relationship of Fear of Abandonment and Limerence

Antecedent		ICD				<i>c'</i>	Limerence			
		<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	β		<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	β
FOA	<i>A</i>	0.70	0.04	0.00	0.66		1.55	0.17	0.00	0.50
ICD		-	-	-	-	<i>B</i>	0.67	0.16	0.00	0.23
		R ² =0.43				R ² = 0.46				
		F (1, 330) = 253.3, p<.001				F (2, 329) = 137.6, p<.001				

Note. *p<0.001; FOA= Fear of Abandonment, ICD= Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions, *B*= Unstandardized Coefficient, *SE*= Standard Error, β = Standardized Coefficient.

A mediation analysis was conducted using the PROCESS macro for SPSS (version 4.2), Model 4 as outlined by Hayes (2022) to investigate whether interpersonal cognitive distortions mediate the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence among young adults. The first regression model assessed the impact of fear of abandonment on interpersonal cognitive distortions. The model was significant as $F(1, 330) = 253.3, p < .001$, explaining 43.4% of the variance in interpersonal cognitive distortions $R^2=0.434$. The results indicate that fear of abandonment significantly predicts interpersonal cognitive distortions as ($B = 0.70, SE = 0.044, t(330) = 15.91, p < .001$), with a 95% confidence interval [0.617, 0.791]. The standardized coefficient for fear of abandonment was $\beta = 0.66$, indicating a strong positive relationship between fear of abandonment and interpersonal cognitive distortions.

The second model examined the effect of fear of abandonment and interpersonal cognitive distortions on limerence. This model was also significant as $F(2, 329) = 137.6, p <$

.001, accounting for 45.5% of the variance in limerence $R^2 = 0.455$. Both fear of abandonment and interpersonal cognitive distortions were significant predictors of limerence. Fear of abandonment had a coefficient of ($B = 1.55$, $SE = 0.17$, $t(329) = 9.24$, $p < .001$) with a 95% confidence interval [1.217, 1.875], and a standardized coefficient of $\beta = 0.500$. Interpersonal cognitive distortions also significantly predict limerence as ($B = 0.67$, $SE = 0.16$, $t(329) = 4.270$, $p < .001$) with a 95% confidence interval [0.361, 0.977], and a standardized coefficient of $\beta = 0.231$.

The total effect model assessed the direct relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence without considering the mediator. This model was significant, $F(1, 330) = 244.170$, $p < .001$, with an $R^2 = 0.42$, indicating that fear of abandonment accounted for 42.5% of the variance in limerence. The results show that fear of abandonment had a significant total effect on limerence, $B = 2.01$, $SE = 0.13$, $t(330) = 15.63$, $p < .001$, with a 95% confidence interval [1.763, 2.270]. The standardized coefficient was $\beta = 0.65$.

The indirect effect of fear of abandonment on limerence through interpersonal cognitive distortions was estimated using 5000 bootstrap samples, and the confidence intervals indicated a significant mediation effect. The indirect effect was $B = 0.47$, with a bootstrap standard error (BootSE) of 0.11 and a 95% bootstrap confidence interval [0.243, 0.702]. The completely standardized indirect effect was $\beta = 0.15$, with a BootSE of 0.037 and a 95% bootstrap confidence interval [0.080, 0.224].

Conclusion. The findings support the hypothesis that interpersonal cognitive distortions mediate the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence. The significant total effect of fear of abandonment on limerence indicates that individuals with higher fear of abandonment are more likely to experience limerence. This effect remains significant but is reduced when

accounting for the mediating role of interpersonal cognitive distortions, indicating partial mediation. The significant indirect effect demonstrates that a portion of the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence operates through the influence of interpersonal cognitive distortions.

Figure 1: Complementary Mediation Between FOA and Limerence through ICD Intimacy Avoidance, Unrealistic Expectations, Interpersonal Misperception as Mediators in the Relationship of Fear of Abandonment and Limerence

The fifth hypothesis was formulated to check whether the subscales of interpersonal cognitive distortions including (intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, interpersonal misperception) play mediating roles in the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence. The hypothesis formulated is as follow.

H5: Intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, and interpersonal misperception play mediating roles in the relationship of fear of abandonment and limerence among young adults.

Mediation Analysis Using PROCESS Macro was utilised to check this hypothesis because it allows to explore how fear of abandonment influences limerence by introducing multiple intermediary variables. Unlike other analytical techniques, mediation analysis can partition the total effect into direct and indirect effects, providing a nuanced understanding of both the direct impact of fear of abandonment on limerence and the indirect impact mediated by multiple mediators.

Table

Mediating Effect of Intimacy Avoidance, Unrealistic Expectations, & Interpersonal Misperception in the Relationship of Fear of Abandonment and Limerence

Antecedent	IA				URE				IM				Limerence							
	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	β	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	β	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	β	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	β				
FOA	<i>a</i> ₁	0.32	0.02	0.00	0.62	<i>a</i> ₂	0.29	.025	0.00	0.54	<i>a</i> ₃	0.09	0.01	0.00	0.38	<i>c</i> '	1.57	0.17	0.00	0.51
IA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₁	0.33	0.34	0.32	0.05
URE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₂	0.86	0.29	0.00	0.15
IM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>b</i> ₃	0.90	0.58	0.12	0.07
		R ² = 0.38				R ² = 0.29				R ² =0.15				R ² = 0.46						
		F (1, 330) = 205.48, p<.001				F (1, 330) = 133.24, p<.001				F (1, 330) = 56.01, p<.001				F (4, 327) = 68.95, p<.001						

Table 8, the mediation analysis was used utilizing a multiple mediator model (Model 4 in PROCESS), with fear of abandonment as the independent variable, limerence as the dependent variable, and intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, and interpersonal misperception as the mediators. The total effect of fear of abandonment on limerence was significant (Effect = 2.017, SE = 0.129, $t = 15.626$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [1.763, 2.270]), with a standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.65$. The direct effect of fear of abandonment on limerence also remained significant after accounting for the mediators (Effect = 1.574, SE = 0.169, $t = 9.290$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [1.240, 1.907]), with a standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.50$. The total indirect effect of fear of abandonment on limerence through the three mediators was significant (Effect = 0.443, BootSE = 0.121, 95% CI [0.213, 0.695]). This suggests that intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, and interpersonal misperception collectively mediate the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence.

The indirect effect of fear of abandonment on limerence through intimacy avoidance was not significant (Effect = 0.105, BootSE = 0.101, 95% CI [-0.095, 0.313]). The standardized indirect effect was 0.034 (BootSE = 0.033, 95% CI [-0.031, 0.101]). Moreover, the indirect effect of fear of abandonment on limerence through unrealistic relationship expectations was significant (Effect = 0.253, BootSE = 0.085, 95% CI [0.090, 0.426]) and the standardized indirect effect was 0.082 (BootSE = 0.027, 95% CI [0.029, 0.136]).

The results also revealed that the indirect effect of fear of abandonment on limerence through interpersonal misperception was not significant (Effect = 0.085, BootSE = 0.057, 95% CI [-0.020, 0.209]). And the standardized indirect effect was 0.028 (BootSE = 0.018, 95% CI [-0.007, 0.066]). The model summary for intimacy avoidance indicates that 38% of the variance in intimacy avoidance is explained by fear of abandonment. This model is highly significant, as

evidenced by the F-value (205.48) with a p-value less than .001. This means that fear of abandonment is a strong predictor of intimacy avoidance among young adults. For unrealistic expectations, the model explains 29% of the variance. The F-value of 133.24 is significant at $p < .001$, indicating that fear of abandonment significantly predicts unrealistic expectations. This substantial portion of variance explained by the model suggests that fear of abandonment is a critical factor influencing unrealistic beliefs about relationships. The interpersonal misperception model accounts for 15% of the variance. The F-value of 56.01, with a p-value less than .001, confirms that fear of abandonment significantly predicts interpersonal misperception. Although the explained variance is smaller compared to the other mediators, it still highlights a significant relationship between fear of abandonment and interpersonal misperception. The model summary for limerence, which includes the mediators intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, and interpersonal misperception, shows that 46% of the variance in limerence is explained by the combined predictors. The F-value of 68.95 is significant at $p < .001$, indicating that the overall model is a strong predictor of limerence. This substantial R^2 value suggests that fear of abandonment and the mediating factors together provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to limerence.

Conclusion. The findings support the hypothesis that intimacy avoidance, unrealistic relationship expectations and interpersonal misperception mediate the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence. The significant total effect of fear of abandonment on limerence indicates that individuals with higher fear of abandonment are more likely to experience limerence. This effect remains significant when accounting for the mediating roles of intimacy avoidance, unrealistic expectations, and interpersonal misperception. However, unrealistic

relationship expectation has a partial mediation in between fear of abandonment and limerence relationship.

Figure 2: Partial Mediation Between FOA and Limerence through URE

Section IV: Summary of Results

This research aimed to explore the ways in which interpersonal cognitive distortions mediate the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence. The results indicated that fear of abandonment was significantly associated with both interpersonal cognitive distortions, its sub-domains including intimacy avoidance, unrealistic relationship expectations, and interpersonal misperception and limerence. Interpersonal cognitive distortions were found to mediate the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence. And unrealistic relationship expectations showed complementary mediation between these variables. Gender and relationship status were also found to influence the relationships between these variables. Specifically, women scored higher than men to experience fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence. Additionally, those who were currently in a relationship showed lower levels of fear of abandonment and limerence compared to those who had never been in a relationship or were no longer in a relationship. People who were in a complicated or uncertain relationship scored highest in terms of study variables. Overall, the study provides important insights into how fear of abandonment can lead to distorted thinking and intense romantic feelings, and how these effects can vary based on gender and relationship status.

Chapter V

Discussion

The aim of this research was to investigate the relationships between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions including intimacy avoidance, unrealistic relationship expectations, interpersonal misperception and limerence. It also aimed to explore the mediating role of interpersonal cognitive distortions, intimacy avoidance, unrealistic relationship expectations, and interpersonal misperception in the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence. Another objective of this research was to explore whether there are any differences in terms of study variables among different gender groups (men, women) and relationship status groups (never been in a relationship, currently single with the history of breakup, in a relationship, and in a complicated relationship/situationship).

For this research, a total of five hypotheses were generated. The first hypothesis was accepted, and it was found that there is a significant positive relationship between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence. The second and third hypotheses were accepted, and it was found that there are significant differences in terms of study variables among different gender and relationship status groups. The fourth hypothesis was related to mediation, it was also accepted, and results showed that interpersonal cognitive distortions have a significant mediating effect in the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence. Consequently, the subscales of interpersonal cognitive distortions i.e, intimacy avoidance, unrealistic relationship expectations and interpersonal misperception also have mediating effects on the relationship between fear of abandonment and limerence.

Existing Literature Supporting Study Findings

Fear of abandonment was found to be significantly positively related to limerence. This finding is particularly new as there is no previous literature studying these two variables together. However, research by Bélanger et al. (2021) revealed that fear of abandonment mediates the relationship between obsessive passion and obsessive relational intrusion suggesting that individuals having fear of abandonment are more likely to get obsessed with their romantic partners and invade their privacy leading to abusive relationships. Fear of abandonment is a core symptom of borderline personality disorder, and research shows that individuals with borderline personality traits including emotional dysregulation and fear of abandonment causes extreme anxiety, obsessive thinking and compulsive behaviors related to romantic partners.

Young's schema theory (Young et al., 2003) suggests that like all early maladaptive schemas, the schema of abandonment leads towards maladaptive coping mechanism. One of them is schema overcompensation i.e, when schema of abandonment is triggered, the individual will try to act completely opposite of it to overcompensate the abandonment core belief by clinging to the romantic partner, getting obsessed with them and showing compulsive behaviors.

Furthermore, fear of abandonment was significantly positively related with interpersonal cognitive distortions. According to Beck, maladaptive schemas, core beliefs, assumptions and rules are the underline basis of automatic thoughts and cognitive distortions which evolve from subjective interpretations of events and adversities (Beck & Beck, 2011). Individuals having core belief of abandonment mostly develop cognitive distortions including all or none thinking (Ociskova et al., 2023), personalization, jumping to conclusion, self-fulfilling prophecy, and mind reading. These cognitive distortions when manifest in relationships cause interpersonal difficulties. Fear of abandonment was found to be significantly positively correlated with

intimacy avoidance which is supported by the previous literature fear of abandonment has a positive relationship with fear of intimacy indicating that individuals having schema of abandonment will avoid intimacy in relationships (Faraji & Ertan, 2023). There was a significant positive relationship between fear of abandonment and unrealistic relationship expectations and the findings are consistent with the previous research findings that people with schema of abandonment develop idealized and unrealistic views about interpersonal relationships as a coping to alleviate their anxious attachment (Navarro-Gómez et al., 2017). These individuals set irrational high standards for their intimate partners (Smith & South, 2020), and they also expect them to provide constant reassurance and seek their validation so that they can alleviate their fear of abandonment (Drapeau et al., 2012).

Lastly, fear of abandonment was significantly positively correlated with interpersonal misperception, and this finding also corroborates with previous studies. Interpersonal misperception is defined as the cognitive distortion in which the individuals attempt to understand other cognitions, and emotions with the help of irrational methods i.e., mind reading and jumping to the conclusion cognitive distortion (Hamamcı, 2004). Research by Bertsch et al. (2018) concludes that individuals with borderline personality traits are more likely to misunderstand the social cues, and intentions of their interpersonal relations. Thus, heightened fear of abandonment leads towards intensified sensitivity and hypervigilance in interpersonal relationships. This causes these individuals to perceive unrealistic rejection and hostility from their relationships (Foxhall et al., 2019).

There is limited research available on limerence and this study found significant associations of limerence with other study variables. A significant relationship was found between limerence and interpersonal cognitive distortions and its subdomains including intimacy

avoidance, unrealistic relationship expectation, and interpersonal misperception. The findings are consistent with limited literature. Research conducted by Bartholomew (1990) suggests that individuals who experience romantic obsession or limerence, have fear of intimacy because deep inside they perceive themselves as unworthy of love, affection, and emotional connection. Avoidance of intimacy acts as a defense mechanism for them so that they can protect themselves from rejection or disappointment (Bartholomew, 1990). They might develop a pattern of avoiding reciprocal relationships to maintain their fantasy and idealized world.

The significant positive relationship between limerence and unrealistic relationship expectation can be supported by the study conducted by Willmott and Bentley (2015) which concluded that individuals suffering from limerence idealize their limerent object (LO) and expects reciprocation from them. Such unrealistic expectations from their LOs can lead to emotional dysregulation, dissatisfaction, and relationship instability if their desire of reciprocation from LO is not met. As in real life, exaggerated and idealistic relationships are unable to meet the expectations created by individuals suffering from limerence (Djickic & Oatley, 2004). Finally, limerence was significantly positively related with interpersonal misperception. Research supports that individuals suffering from romantic obsession have the tendency to jump to the conclusions and misinterpret cues by limerent object. Limerent individuals interpret the thoughts and emotions of limerent object intuitively without any communication based on their own assumptions and desires. This misperception leads to misunderstandings and intense interpersonal difficulties in their relationships (Tennov, 1979).

The results found significant gender differences in terms of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence with women rating higher on these variables than men. Previous literature shows that borderline personality disorder is more prevalent in

women as compared to men (Bozzatello et al., 2024; Qian et al., 2022). Since, fear of abandonment is the core feature of borderline personality disorder (APA, 2022) so this finding can be supported by the research done to explore gender differences in terms of BPD because there is no previous research available exploring gender differences in terms of fear of abandonment. The reasons behind this sex difference are still not known but there are cultural and neurobiological plausible explanations. One plausible explanation could be that borderline personality disorder and borderline personality traits are highly correlated with the history of child sexual abuse. And worldwide statistics showed that 1 in 5 girls is a victim of child sexual abuse as compared to men 1 in 20 boys is a victim of child sexual abuse. So, this might be a possible reason of increased prevalence of fear of abandonment in women than men.

Similarly, women scored higher on limerence than men. These results are supported by the literature. Research conducted by Bode and Kavanagh (2024) suggests that women experience more obsessive thinking, intense emotions, and compulsive behaviours in love than men. Other research also supports the finding that women are more romantically obsessed than men in intimate relationships (Frazier & Esterly, 1990; Hendrick et al., 2006). Research by Singh (2012) concluded that married and unmarried women scored higher on romantic obsession than married and unmarried men. However, (Tennov, 1979) didn't find any gender differences in terms of limerence.

The results revealed that the relationship status has a significant impact on the levels of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence among young adults. It was found that individuals who have never been in a relationship have the lowest levels of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence as compared to those who are currently single with a history of breakup, those who are in a relationship, and those who are in a

complicated relationship. These findings are supported by previous research which concludes that individuals who have never been in a romantic relationship, they never went through the emotional chaos of relationship breakups and relationship conflicts which precipitates and perpetuate the fear of abandonment (Slotter et al., 2010).

The results showed that relationship status has a significant impact on the levels of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence among young adults. It was revealed that individuals who have never been in a relationship have the lowest levels of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence. And people who are currently single with a history of breakup, those who are in a relationship, and those who are in a complicated relationship had the highest levels of these variables. These findings are supported by previous research which concludes that individuals who have never been in a romantic relationship, they never went through the emotional chaos of relationship breakups and relationship conflicts which precipitates and perpetuate the fear of abandonment (Slotter et al., 2010). In contrast, it was found that individuals who are currently single with a history of breakup(s) showed higher levels of fear of abandonment. This might be because of their past breakup experiences in romantic relationships which precipitated their fear of abandonment in future relationships (Frankel, 2023). Similarly, individuals who are currently in situationship or complicated relationships showed highest levels of fear of abandonment. Complicated relationships are marked by uncertainty, ambiguity and emotional complexity (West & Salk, 1987) which might instill a threat of romantic partner to leave and trigger fear of abandonment (Honeycutt, 1985). Correspondingly, there was no significant difference found between individuals who were in a relationship and those who were in a complicated relationship. It

indicates that both groups experience relationship uncertainty and lead towards development of fear of abandonment (Honeycutt,1985).

The findings revealed that individuals who are currently single but have a history of breakup(s) show higher levels of interpersonal cognitive distortions than those who were never in a relationship. It can be inferred that past relationship breakups can inculcate negative core beliefs about oneself and others (Frankel, 2023). It was also found that those who were in a complicated relationship or situationship had the highest levels of interpersonal cognitive distortions. This might be because of ongoing uncertain relationships which can strengthen and intensify interpersonal distorted thinking (Honeycutt,1985).

Furthermore, the findings of the present study revealed that individuals who were never in a relationship scored lowest in limerence. It can be interpreted as these individuals never experienced the emotional turmoil, the highs and lows of a romantic relationship (Slotter et al., 2010). The results showed that individuals who are currently single but had experience of relationships in the past showed higher levels of limerence. It is supported by the previous research conducted by Spielmann et al. (2015) who proposed that individuals having fear of being left alone, find it difficult to let go their ex-partners and they long for them. Highest levels of limerence were found in individuals who were in a complicated relationship or situationship marked by uncertainty. This finding can be linked with the experience of limerence which is an emotionally intense state driven by uncertainty (Carswell & Impett, 2021). The more uncertainty the more they are preoccupied with their limerent objects or romantic partners (Wyant, 2021).

Research Findings in the Light of Cultural Context

In countries like Pakistan where collectivistic culture is followed, there is a strong emphasis on familial bonds. There is a deep-rooted interdependence among family members in a

collectivistic culture (Ayub et al., 2022). The familial bonds are characterized by their intensity and permanence in Pakistan (Ramzan & Amjad, 2017). In these collectivistic cultures, an individual derives their social identity and personal worth from one's role and acceptance within the family unit (Ayub et al., 2022). Moreover, in Pakistan children are raised in close-knit families where multiple generations often live together and maintain strong ties (Aamir, 2004). Children learn to rely heavily on their parents and extended family members for emotional and substantial support, inculcating a profound dependency that extends into their adulthood (Zaman, 2013). This dependency is not only practical but also emotional which leads to an increased sensitivity to any signs of potential abandonment. Furthermore, children develop anxious or avoidant attachment styles due to high emphasis on close familial bonds and dependency (Irfan et al., 2023). As established earlier in the literature review chapter, these childhood attachment patterns can persist into adulthood causing pervasive fear of abandonment. Such an environment sets a stage for heightened anxiety around abandonment, as the consequences of being excluded or left out are perceived as catastrophic.

Within Pakistani cultural framework, there is a pressure to conform to societal and familial norms which can lead individuals to suppress personal desires and emotions for their partners (Ramzan & Amjad, 2017). It results in a reluctance to engage deeply in intimate relationships. This avoidance is a defensive mechanism to prevent conflicts and maintain social harmony, which are highly valued in collectivistic societies. Furthermore, to ensure that children adhere to cultural and familial norms parents often impose strict rules and high expectations on their children, in Pakistan (Sarwar, 2016). This approach suppresses emotional expression and the development of individual autonomy. Meanwhile, children learn to prioritize their family's expectations over their own needs leading to unrealistic relationship expectations. They may

grow up with an idealized conception of relationships, believing that others should inherently understand and fulfil their unspoken needs and desires. It reflects a lack of realistic interpersonal understanding (Ramzan & Amjad, 2017). Moreover, direct confrontation and open discussions about personal feelings and issues in familial and romantic relationships are discouraged due to cultural norms (Khuhro et al., 2021). This communication gap fosters a reliance on implicit expectations and assumptions. This reliance further leads to misperceptions and misunderstandings. Individuals may engage in mind reading, assuming they know what others think or feel without verbal confirmation, resulting in interpersonal misperception (Çayir & Kalkan, 2018).

Pakistani and Indian dramas, movies and songs frequently depict romantic love in an idealized and dramatic fashion. They emphasize the intense emotional experiences, grand gestures, and often unrealistic scenarios (Toor et al., 2023). Such depictions create a cultural script for love that is highly romanticized. It sets unrealistic expectations for real-life relationships among young adults and especially women (Latif et al., 2021). Because women are conditioned to value relational success may be more vulnerable to limerence. Viewers internalize these exaggerated depictions of love which is influenced by these narratives (Toor et al., 2023). It further leads to the initiation of limerence, where the object of affection is idealized and pursued with intense passion (Latif et al., 2021). This media influence shapes how individuals perceive love and romance, promoting an obsessive approach to romantic relationships.

The maladaptive parenting style prevalent in many Pakistani families involves strict control over children's social interactions and emotional expression (Zaman, 2013). This upbringing often limits opportunities for children to develop healthy and balanced views of romantic relationships. When emotional needs are suppressed, individuals find themselves ill-

equipped to navigate the complications of adult romantic relationships (Sarwar, 2016). As a result, they may experience limerence as they seek to fulfil unmet emotional needs from childhood.

In Pakistani culture, gender roles are clearly defined, with definite expectations for men and women. Women are conventionally given the roles that emphasize emotional sensitivity and relational interdependence as caregivers and nurturers (Ali et al., 2011). Subsequently, women's sense of self-worth and security is often closely tied to the stability of their relationships thus they may develop a more acute fear of abandonment (Quintana et al., 2023). Furthermore, one of the most significant cultural practices is the expectation that women will marry and leave their parental homes to join their husbands' families. From a young age, girls are prepared and trained by their parents for this concluding departure (Ahmed, 2022). It instils a sense of future separation and potential loss. This preparation can heighten sensitivity to abandonment, as women are constantly reminded of their future role in a new family and the necessity of adapting to it. The pressure to successfully fit in into their in-laws' household can make women particularly vulnerable to fears of interpersonal instability and rejection.

Limitations and Suggestions

This comprehensive research also had some limitations. Firstly, the data was collected from participants using self-reported tools to assess fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions, and limerence. The self-reported measures are subjected to social desirability bias thus, the results of the study might be affected. In future, qualitative data should also be incorporated to get an in-depth understanding of these variables and address this limitation. Secondly, the study used a cross-sectional design which limits the ability to establish causal inferences and is unable to draw conclusions about changes in study variables over the course of

time. In future, longitudinal studies should be done to measure these variables over time and draw inferences. Future studies should also focus on studying these variables in different cultures of Pakistan to investigate any cultural differences as this study explored the variables in a particular area, restricting the generalizability to other cultures.

Future Implications

The findings of this research have various implications for future research and clinical practice. As the research showed significant relationships between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence, future research should investigate the efficacy of interventions like schema therapy, cognitive behaviour therapy, or dialectical behaviour therapy to treat these complaints among young adults to improve their interpersonal relationships as well as overall wellbeing.

Additionally, this research highlights significant differences across relationship statuses. The results showed that the levels of these variables are particularly higher in individuals in a complicated relationship or situation where there is high uncertainty. Interventions focused on this area should be introduced to address these difficulties in these situations. Similarly, culturally sensitive interventions should be introduced to address these issues in Pakistani youth keeping in view the strong cultural influences.

Awareness seminars should be conducted to educate young adults about harmful impact of dramas, and movies promoting unrealistic views of romantic love on their cognitions, emotions and interpersonal relationships. Policy to control the promotion of content which inculcate these issues in youth, should be made and implemented. Awareness should also be raised to educate parents on healthy parenting style and secure attachment styles. To promote open communication among couples and families, awareness seminars should be conducted.

Furthermore, these findings can be beneficial for the relationship, and couple counsellors as they can assess these issues in young couples because most of the interpersonal issues in relationships are based on cognitive errors.

Television media and social media can play a vital role in spreading awareness regarding these issues among young adults. Short videos and posts can be made on social networking sites to psychoeducate individuals on these issues. Television shows can be done by professionals to talk about these issues in young adults to bring awareness. Self-help manuals can be developed and adapt to address these issues and promote self-care among young adults.

Conclusion

The main objective of this research was to explore the relationship between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence among young adults. Furthermore, it also aimed to investigate the gender and relationship status differences in terms of these study variables. The main objective was achieved by investigating the mediating effects of interpersonal cognitive distortions and its subdomains namely intimacy avoidance, unrealistic relationship expectation, and interpersonal misperceptions in the association between fear of abandonment and limerence. The findings of this research revealed significant relationships which highlights the need of understanding the etiological and developmental factors among young adults specifically in Pakistani culture because these factors are significant contributors of interpersonal ineffectiveness among young adults. The youth in Pakistan is struggling with personal relationship difficulties which needed mental health professional's immediate attention. Furthermore, the findings of this research are important for mental health professionals working in Pakistan around these areas because it will help them in planning intervention plans to address these issues. This research will help in raising awareness around these issues in Pakistani youth

because these are the most neglected areas till date. Furthermore, this research provides valuable insights into the significant gender differences in terms of these variables which needs special attention and in-depth understanding. Similarly, significant differences in terms of study variables among relationship status groups with people in a complicated relationships scoring highest on study variables highlights the significance of studying this phenomenon deeply using qualitative measures. Overall, the study highlights the significance and impact of fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence on mental wellbeing and interpersonal relationships of young adults.

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Appendix A
IRB Approval Form

FORMAN CHRISTIAN COLLEGE
(A CHARTERED UNIVERSITY)

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD
APPROVAL CERTIFICATE

IRB Ref: IRB-569/01-2024

Date: 16-01-2024

Project Title: Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal cognitive distortions, and Limerence among young adults.

Principal Investigator: Muhammad Munib-ur-Rehman

Supervisor: Dr. Ivan Suneel

The Institutional Review Board has examined your project in the IRB meeting held on 16-01-2024 and has approved the proposed study. If during the conduct of your research, any changes occur related to participant risk, study design, confidentiality or consent, or any other change then IRB must be notified immediately.

Please be sure to include the IRB reference number in all correspondence.

Dr. Sharoon Hanook
Convener-IRB
Chairperson Department of Statistics
Forman Christian College
(A Chartered University)
Lahore

Appendix B
ERC Approval Form

Estd 1864

Forman Christian College

(A Chartered University) Lahore

Ethical Review Committee

ERC Ref: PSYC699-23-121

Date: 14 November 2023

Department of Psychology

Subject: ERC approval of BS/MS/MPhil thesis research proposal

Title of the study: Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions, and Limerence among Young adults.

Purpose: The research topic, "Fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence among young adults," holds significant importance for multiple reasons. Firstly, it is crucial for enhancing the psychological well-being of young adults, given the profound influence of variables under study, on their mental health and interpersonal relationships. Secondly, it will provide insights into the dynamics of relationships during a critical developmental period, offering a deeper understanding of how fear of abandonment, limerence, and interpersonal cognitive distortions affect the formation and maintenance of healthy relationships in youth.

Investigator: Muhammad Munib-ur-Rehman

Supervisor: Dr. Ivan Suneel

Restrictions/Remarks: N/A

Note: As a rule material containing live pathogens will not be allowed at the department of Forman Christian College, A Chartered University. Even otherwise, the Chairperson shall be informed of the state of pathogens if being transported to any of the department's labs.

The supervisor shall be responsible for the overall ethical management of the procedures used in the carrying out the said study.

Chairperson
Department Dr. Ivan Suneel

Signature

Name Dr. Ivan Suneel
Chairman, ERC
Department Psychology

Signature

Appendix C
Informed Consent

Study name: Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions and Limerence among Young Adults.

Purpose of the study: The study aims to investigate the relationship between fear of abandonment, interpersonal cognitive distortions and limerence among young adults.

Principle investigator and contact information:

Muhammad Munib-Ur-Rehman

243937832@formanite.fccollege.edu.pk

Supervised by: Dr. Ivan Suneel

Contact information

ivansuneel@fccollege.edu.pk

What you will be asked to do: You are being asked to take part in a research study. Before you decide to participate in this study, it is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take your time to read the following information. If you have any questions or require additional information, please contact the researcher.

Risks and discomforts: There will be no risks and mental or physical harm involved in this study.

You may decline to answer any or all questions and you may choose to withdraw from participating in this study at any time.

Benefits: You will receive no direct benefit from participating in this study. However, we hope that the findings of this study will be useful in providing an awareness towards an area that has not been well researched before and will help bridge the gap in the literature.

Confidentiality: Your responses to this ‘Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions and Limerence among Young Adults’ survey be anonymous. Please do not write any identifying information on your ‘Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive

Distortions and Limerence among Young Adults” survey. The researcher will make every attempt to protect your anonymity, including the following:

- Assigning code names/numbers for participants that will be used on all research notes and documents
- All the confidential data will safely be discarded in such a way that it cannot be retrieved after the completion of this study

Voluntary participation: Your participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part in this study, you will be asked to sign a consent form.

Withdrawal from the study: After you sign the consent form, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. Withdrawing from this study will not affect the relationship you have, if any, with the researcher. If you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, your data will be returned to you or destroyed.

Consent to participate:

I agree to participate in the study titled **Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions and Limerence among Young Adults**. I have been briefed about the aims and objectives of the study and I would like to participate in the study. I am aware of my rights as a research participant. My signature below indicates my consent.

Signature _____

Date: _____

Appendix D
Permissions

Fear of Abandonment

Abandonment Core Belief Scale

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LOVE ME, DON'T LEAVE ME

SELF-ASSESSMENT: ABANDONMENT CORE BELIEF

Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions Scale

25/06/2024, 18:08

FORMAN CHRISTIAN COLLEGE Mail - (no subject)

Muhammad Munib Ur Rehman <243937832@formanite.fccollege.edu.pk>

(no subject)

1 message

zeynep hamamci <zhamamci@gmail.com>
To: 243937832@formanite.fccollege.edu.pk

Fri, Sep 29, 2023 at 11:52 AM

Dear Academician

You can use the measurement tool we developed in your scientific studies. I wish you success in your academic work.

Kind regards

prof. Dr. Zeynep Hamamci

2 attachments

 The Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions Scale.doc
125K

 scale.docx
30K

Muhammad Munib Ur Rehman <243937832@formanite.fccollege.edu.pk>

Permission to use Limerence Scale

3 messages

Muhammad Munib Ur Rehman <243937832@formanite.fccollege.edu.pk>

Tue, Sep 26, 2023 at 10:45 PM

To: "elemay@umd.edu" <elemay@umd.edu>

Dear Mr. Edward Lemay,

I hope this email finds you well. I am a student of Masters of Clinical Psychology at Forman Christian College University, Lahore, Pakistan and I am interested in using scale on Limerence which was developed by (Wolf & Lemay, 2015) . I am doing my final year research under the supervision of head of department of psychology, Dr. Ivan Suneel, titled "Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions, Limerence and Fear of Abandonment among Young Adults". I have found that this scale was the most recent one. And i also have read about the reliability of the tool in assessing limerence and I believe it would greatly contribute to the validity of my research findings. I have read the items in the articles, they are culturally relevant. I kindly request your permission to use your tool for my study.

Thank you for considering my request, and I look forward to your response. It will be a great favor if you attach a PDF or link to assess the tool along with scoring method, information related to scale and cut off scores (If any).

Best Regards,
Muhammad Munib-ur-Rehman,
Trainee Clinical Psychology
MSCP, FC College University, Lahore, Pakistan.

Edward Lemay <elemay@umd.edu>

Wed, Sep 27, 2023 at 1:26 AM

To: Muhammad Munib Ur Rehman <243937832@formanite.fccollege.edu.pk>

Hi Muhammad,

Thanks for your interest in the limerence scale. It is attached to this email, and below is an email Noah wrote to someone else who was also interested in this scale, which contains some useful information about how we administered the scale. Good luck with your research!

All the best,

Ed

Edward Lemay
Professor
Area Head, *Social, Decision, and Organizational Sciences*
Director, *Interpersonal Relationships Lab*
Associate Editor, *Emotion*
Department of Psychology
University of Maryland, College Park
College Park, MD 20742
Pronouns: He/Him/His ([What's this?](#))
Lab website: www.irlumd.weebly.com
Office: Biology / Psychology Building Room 3147B
Office Phone: 301-405-5927
Zoom: <https://umd.zoom.us/j/9180096949>

----- Forwarded message -----

From: **Noah Wolf** <noahwolf1@gmail.com>

Hi,
Thanks for your interest in the Limerence measure Dr. Lemay and I created. We had participants rate the items on the attached measure on a Likert scale (1 - 7 Strongly Disagree - Strongly Agree).

Here is an example of the instructions we gave when distributing the measure along with other questionnaires: *The set of items on the next page concerns your feelings towards someone you feel or have felt romantically attracted*

toward. As such, the feelings referred to in these items pertain to romantic feelings. You do not have to be in a relationship with the person you have romantic feelings for; people often admire others from afar. However, please keep the same romantic interest in mind for the following items on this page and throughout the rest of the survey.

As far as adapting the measure to media figures, you could alter the instructions to request that participants think of a media figure they are attracted to. Here is an example of such an altered wording to the instructions:

*The set of items on the next page concerns your feelings towards **a media figure that you have felt attracted to**. As such, the feelings referred to in these items pertain to romantic feelings. You do not have to be in a relationship with the person you have romantic feelings for; people often admire others from afar. However, please keep the same **media figure** in mind for all of the following items on the next page..*

If you distribute the questionnaire electronically through an interface like Qualtrics.com, you could have the participant type in the name of a media figure after reading the instructions and then set it up so that the media figure's name gets piped in to replace the words "This person" in all of the items (e.g. It is hard to imagine feeling romantic towards anybody else but this person vs. It is hard to imagine feeling romantic towards anybody else but Paul McCartney).

And of course, you have permission to adapt the scale towards media figures. Please feel free to let me know if you have more questions or would like more suggestions.

Best,
Noah Wolf

Edward Lemay
Professor
Area Head, *Social, Decision, and Organizational Sciences*
Director, *Interpersonal Relationships Lab*
Associate Editor, *Emotion*
Department of Psychology
University of Maryland, College Park
College Park, MD 20742
Pronouns: He/Him/His ([What's this?](#))
Lab website: www.irlumd.weebly.com
Office: Biology / Psychology Building Room 3147B
Office Phone: 301-405-5927
Zoom: <https://umd.zoom.us/j/9180096949>

[Quoted text hidden]

 Wolf and Lemay Limerence Measure.docx
10K

Muhammad Munib Ur Rehman <243937832@formanite.fcollege.edu.pk>
To: Edward Lemay <elemay@umd.edu>

Wed, Sep 27, 2023 at 11:10 AM

Thank you so much!

[Quoted text hidden]

FORMAN CHRISTIAN COLLEGE
(A CHARTERED UNIVERSITY)

Date: _____

Permission to Collect Research Data

This is to certify that Mr. Muhammad Munib-Ur-Rehman (registration number: 243937832) is a student of MS Clinical Psychology at Department of Psychology, Forman Christian College (A Chartered University), Lahore and is doing thesis as mandatory degree requirement. He is conducting research on "Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions and Limerence among Young Adults" under the supervision of, Dr. Ivan Suneel. He is interested in carrying out the study in your institution with university students. The research will require participants to fill out the research questionnaires. I request you to grant him permission to conduct the research work at your prestigious institution. It is ensured that the data collected will only be used for research purpose and anonymity and confidentiality of the data will be maintained.

Your cooperation in this regard will be highly appreciated.

Estd. 1864

Sincerely,

Dr. Ivan Suneel

Chairperson Department of Psychology

Forman Christian College (A Chartered University), Lahore

*Allowed to collect
data from the
department*

P. Salma Hasan

Prof. Dr. Syeda Salma Hasan
Chairperson
Department of Psychology
C. University Lahore

📍 Ferozepur Road, Lahore-54600.
☎ PH: 042-99231581-8
🌐 www.fccollege.edu.pk

FORMAN CHRISTIAN COLLEGE (A CHARTERED UNIVERSITY)

Date: _____

Permission to Collect Research Data

This is to certify that Mr. Muhammad Munib-Ur-Rehman (registration number: 243937832) is a student of MS Clinical Psychology at Department of Psychology, Forman Christian College (A Chartered University), Lahore and is doing thesis as mandatory degree requirement. He is conducting research on "Fear of Abandonment, Interpersonal Cognitive Distortions and Limerence among Young Adults" under the supervision of, Dr. Ivan Suneel. He is interested in carrying out the study in your institution with university students. The research will require participants to fill out the research questionnaires. I request you to grant him permission to conduct the research work at your prestigious institution. It is ensured that the data collected will only be used for research purpose and anonymity and confidentiality of the data will be maintained.

Your cooperation in this regard will be highly appreciated.

Estd. 1864

Sincerely,

Dr. Ivan Suneel

Chairperson Department of Psychology

Forman Christian College (A Chartered University), Lahore

Appendix E
Questionnaire Booklet

Socio-demographic Information

Age.....

Gender: Male/ Female/ Other

Relationship Status:

- 1) Never been in a romantic relationship
- 2) Currently single and have a history of past romantic relationship
- 3) In a romantic relationship
- 4) In a complicated/ uncertain relationship or situationship

Education Level: Bachelors (16 years ed.)/ Masters (18-year ed.) PhD (Above 18 years ed.)

Major: Business/ Humanities/ Natural and applied sciences/ Social sciences

FOA

Instructions: Read the following statements carefully and rate them on the given scale according to how you feel or think about that statement. Note that there are no right or wrong answers.

Sr. No.	Statements	completely untrue of me	mostly untrue of me	slightly more true than untrue of me	moderately true of me	mostly true of me	describes me perfectly
1.	I worry a lot that the people I love will die or leave me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
2.	I cling to people because I am afraid, they will leave me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3.	I do not have a stable base of support.	1	2	3	4	5	6
4.	I keep falling in love with people who cannot be there for me in a committed way.	1	2	3	4	5	6
5.	People have always come and gone in my life.	1	2	3	4	5	6
6.	I get desperate when someone I love pulls away.	1	2	3	4	5	6

7.	I get so obsessed with the idea that my lovers will leave me that I drive them away.	1	2	3	4	5	6
8.	The people closest to me are unpredictable. One minute they are there for me and the next minute they are gone.	1	2	3	4	5	6
9.	I need other people too much.	1	2	3	4	5	6
10.	In the end I will be alone.	1	2	3	4	5	6

ICD

Instructions: This scale includes some of the thoughts that people adopt about interpersonal relationships. Please read each sentence carefully and indicate to what extent you agree with these thoughts by considering the options below. Make sure to make a single mark for each statement you read. There are no right or wrong answers to these statements, as each person has a unique personal opinion.

Statements		I do not agree at all	I agree very little	I partially agree	I quite agree	I totally agree
1	Being too friendly with people often creates problems.	1	2	3	4	5
2	People don't understand me at all	1	2	3	4	5
3	True feelings to the people around me if I express my thoughts and they by I believe I rejected	1	2	3	4	5
4	There are no true friends in this life	1	2	3	4	5
5	I want everyone with whom I have a relationship to share all their feelings and thoughts with me.	1	2	3	4	5
6	I can understand what kind of person a person is from the eyes of a person	1	2	3	4	5
7	I can understand what other people are thinking, even if they don't express it.	1	2	3	4	5
8	The other person should be able to understand what I am thinking even if I do not express it .	1	2	3	4	5
9	In order for me to feel good, other people's feelings and thoughts about me should be positive.	1	2	3	4	5
10	People don't keep their promises	1	2	3	4	5
11	I should always be in a social group	1	2	3	4	5
12	I think that in social situations people will not accept me as I am .	1	2	3	4	5
13	It is useful to be constantly alert to the people around us.	1	2	3	4	5
14	I always sacrifice myself in order not to upset the people around me. i have to give	1	2	3	4	5
15	In order to please people in my relationships, I have to act as they want.	1	2	3	4	5
16	I always want someone around me	1	2	3	4	5
17	I want people to always treat me with understanding.	1	2	3	4	5
18	In relationships, people should meet all of each other's expectations.	1	2	3	4	5
19	It's always good to keep it superficial with people .	1	2	3	4	5

WLLS

Instructions: The set of items on the next page concerns your feelings towards someone you feel or have felt romantically attracted toward. As such, the feelings referred to in these items pertain to romantic feelings. You do not have to be in a relationship with the person you have romantic feelings for; people often admire others from afar. However, please keep the same romantic interest in mind for the following items on this page and throughout the rest of the survey.

Sr. No.	Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1.	It is hard to imagine feeling romantic towards anybody else but this person.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2.	Nobody else but this person could make me feel the way I do.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3.	This person is the only person for me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4.	Matters concerning this person are more important to me than any other concern that I have in my life.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5.	I cannot control when or how often I think of this person.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6.	I begin thinking of this person even when I do not will myself to do so.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7.	I cannot seem to get this person out of my mind.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8.	Most of my thoughts concerning this person come about suddenly and without effort.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
9.	I could be wrong about how this person feels about me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
10.	I never seem to be 100% sure of how this person feels about me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
11.	I am unsure of how this person feels about me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
12.	It is possible that this person could feel differently towards me than what I have been led to believe.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
13.	None of this person's negative attributes bother me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
14.	I do not pay any attention to this person's negative attributes.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
15.	To me, this person's negative attributes are charming.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
16.	This person's shortcomings do not bother me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
17.	When I think about this person, I develop an ache in the center of my chest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
18.	The way I feel about this person leaves an aching sensation in the center of my chest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
19.	I experience the longing to be with this person as an aching sensation in the center of my chest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
20.	When this person leaves, I develop an ache in the center of my chest.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
21.	I am extremely happy when I believe this person feels strongly towards me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
22.	If this person felt the same way about me as I do for him/her I would be extremely happy.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
23.	I become overjoyed when I believe this person feels the same way about me as I do for him/her.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
24.	I have a hard time speaking and cannot think clearly around this person.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
25.	I become extremely jittery and nervous around this person.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
26.	When I am around this person, I become uneasy.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
27.	I know that, even if I wanted to, I could not change the way I feel about this person.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
28.	I cannot change the way I feel about this person.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
29.	The feelings I have for this person are impossible to change.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
30.	I feel like I am powerless to change the way that I feel towards this person.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Appendix F
Turnitin Similarity Report

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